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#####
## PPA - FIRST ORDER EFFECTS - Petra Hinterland
## =====
## Project: The Landscape Organization of the Petraean Hinterland
## Author: W.M.Kennedy and D. Knitter
## Version: 01
## Date of last changes: Mitt 26. Oct 12:08:44 CET 2016
## Data: Settlement b, DEM (30m SRTM-1); Geological Map of Petra Map (1:50.000)
## Author of data: Various survey results in Petra area. Acquired by W. M. Kennedy
## Purpose: 1st-Order Effects of point pattern process
## Content: point pattern analysis
## Licence data: -
## Licence Script: -
##
#####
## References
#####
## ref <- citation()
## citation(package="rgdal")
## citation(package="raster")
## citation(package="gdata")
## citation(package="sp")
## citation(package="rgrass7")
##
#####
## Working Directory
#####
#
setwd("G:/Archaeology/Promotion/Daten/Jordan/Point Patterns")
#####
## Point Pattern Analysis (First Order Effects) in R
#####
#
##Packages
#####
#
#install.packages("gdata")
library(gdata)
library(xlsx)
#install.packages("spatstat")
library(spatstat)
#install.packages("sp")
library(sp)
library(rgdal)
#install.packages("plotrix")
library(plotrix)
#install.packages("raster")
library(maptools)
library(raster)
#####
## Archaeological Evidence (and subcategories) as Covariate Data
#####

###Archaeological Evidence###
#####
#Agricultural Installations:
a<- read.xlsx("./2data/Agricultural Installation/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Agricultural Installation.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(a)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(a)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Communication Infrastructures:
b<- read.xlsx("./2data/Communication Infrastructure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Communication Infrastructure.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(b)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(b)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Exploitation/Industrial Sites:
c<- read.xlsx("./2data/Exploitation_Industrial Site/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Exploitation_Industrial Site.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(c)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(c)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
d<- read.xlsx("./2data/Funerary and Commemorative Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Funerary and Commemorative
Structure.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(d)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(d)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Military Structures:
e<- read.xlsx("./2data/Military Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Military Structures.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(e)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(e)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Religious Structures:
f<- read.xlsx("./2data/Religious Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Religious Structure.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(f)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(f)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

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#Settlement:
g<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Settlement.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Unspecified Structures and Features:
h<- read.xlsx("./2data/Unspecified Structures and Features/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Unspecified Structures and
Features.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(h)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(h)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Water Structures:
i<- read.xlsx("./2data/Water Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Water Structures.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(i)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(i)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
###Archaeological Evidence (SUBCATEGORIES)###
#####
#####
#Agricultural Installations:
#####
#Agricultural Processing Installations:
a_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Agricultural Installation/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Agricultural Processing
Installation.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(a_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(a_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Agricultural Storing Installations:
a_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Agricultural Installation/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Agricultural Storing
Installation.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(a_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(a_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Agricultural Terrace/ Fields:
a_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Agricultural Installation/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Agricultural Terrace_Field.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(a_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(a_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Communication Infrastructures:
#####
#Caravanserai:
b_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Communication Infrastructure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Caravanserai.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(b_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(b_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Road Marker:
b_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Communication Infrastructure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Road Marker.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(b_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(b_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Road Station:
b_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Communication Infrastructure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Road Station.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(b_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(b_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Road:
b_4<- read.xlsx("./2data/Communication Infrastructure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Road.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(b_4)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(b_4)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Route/Tracks (naqqb):
b_5<- read.xlsx("./2data/Communication Infrastructure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Route_Track_Naqb.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(b_5)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(b_5)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Exploitation/Industrial Sites:
#####

#Industrial/ Exploitation Installation:
c_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Exploitation_Industrial Site/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Industrial_Exploitation
Installation.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(c_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(c_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
#####

#Cemetery:
d_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Funerary and Commemorative Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Cemetery.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(d_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM

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proj4string(d_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Isolated Funerary Monuments:
d_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Funerary and Commemorative Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Isolated Funerary
Monument.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(d_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(d_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Military Structures:
#####

# Forts:
e_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Military Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Fort.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(e_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(e_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Fortlets:
e_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Military Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Fortlet.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(e_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(e_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Fortresses:
e_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Military Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Fortress.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(e_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(e_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Watchtower:
e_4<- read.xlsx("./2data/Military Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Watchtower.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(e_4)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(e_4)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Religious Structures:
#####

# Isolated Cultic Installation:
f_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Religious Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Isolated Cultic Installation.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(f_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(f_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Sanctuary:
f_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Religious Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Sanctuary.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(f_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(f_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Significant Religious/ Cultic Structure:
f_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Religious Structure/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Significant Religious_Cultic Structure.xlsx",
1)
coordinates(f_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(f_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Settlement:
#####

# City:
g_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ City.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Cluster of Building Structures:
g_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Cluster of Building Structures.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Farm:
g_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Farm.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Town:
g_4<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Town.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g_4)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g_4)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Villa:
g_5<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Villa.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g_5)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g_5)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Village:
g_6<- read.xlsx("./2data/Settlement/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_ Village.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(g_6)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(g_6)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N
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#####
#Unspecified Structures and/or Features:
#####
#Epigraphical Site or Location
h_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Unspecified Structures and Features/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Epigraphical Site or
Location.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(h_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(h_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Find Cluster:
h_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Unspecified Structures and Features/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Find Cluster.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(h_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(h_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Natural Rockcut Structures:
h_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Unspecified Structures and Features/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Natural_Rockcut
Structures.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(h_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(h_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Structures of Undetermined Function:
h_4<- read.xlsx("./2data/Unspecified Structures and Features/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Structures of Undetermined
Function.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(h_4)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(h_4)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Walls of Undetermined Function:
h_5<- read.xlsx("./2data/Unspecified Structures and Features/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Walls of Undetermined
Function.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(h_5)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(h_5)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
#Water Structures:
#####

#Dam/ Barrage:
i_1<- read.xlsx("./2data/Water Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Dam_Barrage.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(i_1)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(i_1)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Spring:
i_2<- read.xlsx("./2data/Water Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Spring.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(i_2)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(i_2)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Water Conduit:
i_3<- read.xlsx("./2data/Water Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Water Conduit.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(i_3)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(i_3)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Water Storage Installation:
i_4<- read.xlsx("./2data/Water Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Water Storage Installation.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(i_4)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(i_4)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#Well
i_5<- read.xlsx("./2data/Water Structures/100AD/MASTER20160921_20KM_Well.xlsx", 1)
coordinates(i_5)<- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(i_5)<- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")## UTM36N

#####
## Setting My.Owin
#####
library(maptools)
poly.owin<- readShapeSpatial("G:/Archaeology/Promotion/Daten/Jordan/Shapefiles/Sonstige/Petra_20km_Radius_UTM.shp")
#20km Radius around Petra

#####
## Creating Point Patterns of Archaeological Evidence (and subcategories)
#####
ppp.window<- as.owin(poly.owin)

a.pp<- ppp(x=a@coords[,1], y=a@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(a.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

a_1.pp<- ppp(x=a_1@coords[,1], y=a_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(a_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

a_2.pp<- ppp(x=a_2@coords[,1], y=a_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(a_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

a_3.pp<- ppp(x=a_3@coords[,1], y=a_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(a_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

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b.pp<- ppp(x=b@coords[,1], y=b@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(b.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

b_1.pp<- ppp(x=b_1@coords[,1], y=b_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(b_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

b_2.pp<- ppp(x=b_2@coords[,1], y=b_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(b_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

b_3.pp<- ppp(x=b_3@coords[,1], y=b_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(b_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

b_4.pp<- ppp(x=b_4@coords[,1], y=b_4@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(b_4.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

b_5.pp<- ppp(x=b_5@coords[,1], y=b_5@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(b_5.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

c.pp<- ppp(x=c@coords[,1], y=c@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(c.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

c_1.pp<- ppp(x=c_1@coords[,1], y=c_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(c_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

d.pp<- ppp(x=d@coords[,1], y=d@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(d.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

d_1.pp<- ppp(x=d_1@coords[,1], y=d_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(d_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

d_2.pp<- ppp(x=d_2@coords[,1], y=d_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(d_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

e.pp<- ppp(x=e@coords[,1], y=e@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(e.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

e_1.pp<- ppp(x=e_1@coords[,1], y=e_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(e_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

e_2.pp<- ppp(x=e_2@coords[,1], y=e_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(e_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

e_3.pp<- ppp(x=e_3@coords[,1], y=e_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(e_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

e_4.pp<- ppp(x=e_4@coords[,1], y=e_4@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(e_4.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

f.pp<- ppp(x=f@coords[,1], y=f@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(f.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

f_1.pp<- ppp(x=f_1@coords[,1], y=f_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(f_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

f_2.pp<- ppp(x=f_2@coords[,1], y=f_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(f_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

f_3.pp<- ppp(x=f_3@coords[,1], y=f_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(f_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g.pp<- ppp(x=g@coords[,1], y=g@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g_1.pp<- ppp(x=g_1@coords[,1], y=g_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g_2.pp<- ppp(x=g_2@coords[,1], y=g_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g_3.pp<- ppp(x=g_3@coords[,1], y=g_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g_4.pp<- ppp(x=g_4@coords[,1], y=g_4@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g_4.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g_5.pp<- ppp(x=g_5@coords[,1], y=g_5@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g_5.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

g_6.pp<- ppp(x=g_6@coords[,1], y=g_6@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(g_6.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

h.pp<- ppp(x=h@coords[,1], y=h@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(h.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")
```

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h_1.pp<- ppp(x=h_1@coords[,1], y=h_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(h_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

h_2.pp<- ppp(x=h_2@coords[,1], y=h_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(h_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

h_3.pp<- ppp(x=h_3@coords[,1], y=h_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(h_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

h_4.pp<- ppp(x=h_4@coords[,1], y=h_4@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(h_4.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

h_5.pp<- ppp(x=h_5@coords[,1], y=h_5@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(h_5.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

i.pp<- ppp(x=i@coords[,1], y=i@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(i.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

i_1.pp<- ppp(x=i_1@coords[,1], y=i_1@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(i_1.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

i_2.pp<- ppp(x=i_2@coords[,1], y=i_2@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(i_2.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

i_3.pp<- ppp(x=i_3@coords[,1], y=i_3@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(i_3.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

i_4.pp<- ppp(x=i_4@coords[,1], y=i_4@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(i_4.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

i_5.pp<- ppp(x=i_5@coords[,1], y=i_5@coords[,2], window=ppp.window)
unitname(i_5.pp)<- c("meter", "meters")

#####
#=====
# Researching Intensities of Patterns
#=====
#####

#=====
## Read Petra Shape
#####
petra<- readShapeSpatial("./data/PetraUTM.shp")
#=====

#=====
#Measures of Central Tendency
#=====
#Mean center (mc) and standard distance (stdist):

#Agricultural Installations:
mc<- cbind(sum(a@coords[,1])/length(a@coords[,1]),
           sum(a@coords[,2])/length(a@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((a@coords[,1]-mean(a@coords[,1]))^2+
                (a@coords[,2]-mean(a@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(a@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Agricultural Installations")
points(a.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names(table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_a.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(a_1@coords[,1])/length(a_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(a_1@coords[,2])/length(a_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((a_1@coords[,1]-mean(a_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (a_1@coords[,2]-mean(a_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(a_1@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Agricultural Processing Installations")
points(a_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)

```

```

with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_a_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(a_2@coords[,1])/length(a_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(a_2@coords[,2])/length(a_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((a_2@coords[,1]-mean(a_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (a_2@coords[,2]-mean(a_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(a_2@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Agricultural Storing Installations")
points(a_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_a_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(a_3@coords[,1])/length(a_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(a_3@coords[,2])/length(a_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((a_3@coords[,1]-mean(a_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (a_3@coords[,2]-mean(a_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(a_3@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
points(a_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_a_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Communication Infrastructures:
mc<- cbind(sum(b@coords[,1])/length(b@coords[,1]),
           sum(b@coords[,2])/length(b@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((b@coords[,1]-mean(b@coords[,1]))^2+
                (b@coords[,2]-mean(b@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(b@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Communication Infrastructures")
points(b.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_b.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(b_1@coords[,1])/length(b_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(b_1@coords[,2])/length(b_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((b_1@coords[,1]-mean(b_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (b_1@coords[,2]-mean(b_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(b_1@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")

```

```

plot(poly.owin, main= "Caravanserai")
points(b_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_b_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(b_2@coords[,1])/length(b_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(b_2@coords[,2])/length(b_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((b_2@coords[,1]-mean(b_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (b_2@coords[,2]-mean(b_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(b_2@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Road Markers")
points(b_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_b_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(b_3@coords[,1])/length(b_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(b_3@coords[,2])/length(b_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((b_3@coords[,1]-mean(b_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (b_3@coords[,2]-mean(b_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(b_3@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Road Stations")
points(b_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_b_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(b_4@coords[,1])/length(b_4@coords[,1]),
           sum(b_4@coords[,2])/length(b_4@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((b_4@coords[,1]-mean(b_4@coords[,1]))^2+
                (b_4@coords[,2]-mean(b_4@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(b_4@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_4.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Roads")
points(b_4.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_b_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(b_5@coords[,1])/length(b_5@coords[,1]),
           sum(b_5@coords[,2])/length(b_5@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((b_5@coords[,1]-mean(b_5@coords[,1]))^2+
                (b_5@coords[,2]-mean(b_5@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(b_5@coords[,1]))

```

```

length(b_5@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_5.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Route/ Tracks (naqb)")
points(b_5.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_b_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Exploitation/ Industrial Sites:

mc<- cbind(sum(c@coords[,1])/length(c@coords[,1]),
           sum(c@coords[,2])/length(c@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((c@coords[,1]-mean(c@coords[,1]))^2+
                 (c@coords[,2]-mean(c@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(c@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/c.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
points(c.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_c.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(c_1@coords[,1])/length(c_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(c_1@coords[,2])/length(c_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((c_1@coords[,1]-mean(c_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                 (c_1@coords[,2]-mean(c_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(c_1@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/c_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Industrial/ Exploitation Installation")
points(c_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_c_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:

mc<- cbind(sum(d@coords[,1])/length(d@coords[,1]),
           sum(d@coords[,2])/length(d@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((d@coords[,1]-mean(d@coords[,1]))^2+
                 (d@coords[,2]-mean(d@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(d@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
points(d.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_d.pp.csv", sep = ";")

```

```

mc<- cbind(sum(d_1@coords[,1])/length(d_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(d_1@coords[,2])/length(d_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((d_1@coords[,1]-mean(d_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (d_1@coords[,2]-mean(d_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(d_1@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Cemeteries")
points(d_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_d_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(d_2@coords[,1])/length(d_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(d_2@coords[,2])/length(d_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((d_2@coords[,1]-mean(d_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (d_2@coords[,2]-mean(d_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(d_2@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Isolated Funerary Monuments")
points(d_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_d_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Military Structures:
mc<- cbind(sum(e@coords[,1])/length(e@coords[,1]),
           sum(e@coords[,2])/length(e@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((e@coords[,1]-mean(e@coords[,1]))^2+
                (e@coords[,2]-mean(e@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(e@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Military Structures")
points(e.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_e.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(e_1@coords[,1])/length(e_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(e_1@coords[,2])/length(e_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((e_1@coords[,1]-mean(e_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (e_1@coords[,2]-mean(e_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(e_1@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Forts")
points(e_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

```

```

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_e_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(e_2@coords[,1])/length(e_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(e_2@coords[,2])/length(e_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((e_2@coords[,1]-mean(e_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (e_2@coords[,2]-mean(e_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(e_2@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Fortlets")
points(e_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_e_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(e_3@coords[,1])/length(e_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(e_3@coords[,2])/length(e_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((e_3@coords[,1]-mean(e_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (e_3@coords[,2]-mean(e_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(e_3@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Fortresses")
points(e_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_e_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(e_4@coords[,1])/length(e_4@coords[,1]),
           sum(e_4@coords[,2])/length(e_4@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((e_4@coords[,1]-mean(e_4@coords[,1]))^2+
                (e_4@coords[,2]-mean(e_4@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(e_4@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e_4.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Watchtower")
points(e_4.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_e_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Religious Structures:
mc<- cbind(sum(f@coords[,1])/length(f@coords[,1]),
           sum(f@coords[,2])/length(f@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((f@coords[,1]-mean(f@coords[,1]))^2+
                (f@coords[,2]-mean(f@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(f@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Religious Structures")
points(f.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)

```

```

with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_f.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(f_1@coords[,1])/length(f_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(f_1@coords[,2])/length(f_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((f_1@coords[,1]-mean(f_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (f_1@coords[,2]-mean(f_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(f_1@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Isolated Cultic Installations")
points(f_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_f_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(f_2@coords[,1])/length(f_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(f_2@coords[,2])/length(f_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((f_2@coords[,1]-mean(f_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (f_2@coords[,2]-mean(f_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(f_2@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Sanctuaries")
points(f_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_f_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(f_3@coords[,1])/length(f_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(f_3@coords[,2])/length(f_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((f_3@coords[,1]-mean(f_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (f_3@coords[,2]-mean(f_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(f_3@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Significant Religious/ Cultic Structure")
points(f_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_f_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Settlements:
mc<- cbind(sum(g@coords[,1])/length(g@coords[,1]),
           sum(g@coords[,2])/length(g@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g@coords[,1]-mean(g@coords[,1]))^2+
                (g@coords[,2]-mean(g@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(g@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")

```

```

plot(poly.owin, main= "Settlements")
points(g.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(g_1@coords[,1])/length(g_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(g_1@coords[,2])/length(g_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g_1@coords[,1]-mean(g_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (g_1@coords[,2]-mean(g_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(g_1@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Cities")
points(g_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(g_2@coords[,1])/length(g_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(g_2@coords[,2])/length(g_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g_2@coords[,1]-mean(g_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (g_2@coords[,2]-mean(g_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(g_2@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Cluster of Building Structures")
points(g_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(g_3@coords[,1])/length(g_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(g_3@coords[,2])/length(g_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g_3@coords[,1]-mean(g_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (g_3@coords[,2]-mean(g_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(g_3@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Farms")
points(g_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(g_4@coords[,1])/length(g_4@coords[,1]),
           sum(g_4@coords[,2])/length(g_4@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g_4@coords[,1]-mean(g_4@coords[,1]))^2+

```

```

      (g_4@coords[,2]-mean(g_4@coords[,2]))^2) /
      length(g_4@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_4.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Towns")
points(g_4.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(g_5@coords[,1])/length(g_5@coords[,1]),
           sum(g_5@coords[,2])/length(g_5@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g_5@coords[,1]-mean(g_5@coords[,1]))^2+
                (g_5@coords[,2]-mean(g_5@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(g_5@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_5.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Villae")
points(g_5.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(g_6@coords[,1])/length(g_6@coords[,1]),
           sum(g_6@coords[,2])/length(g_6@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((g_6@coords[,1]-mean(g_6@coords[,1]))^2+
                (g_6@coords[,2]-mean(g_6@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(g_6@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_6.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Villages")
points(g_6.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_g_6.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Unspecified Structures and/ or Features:

mc<- cbind(sum(h@coords[,1])/length(h@coords[,1]),
           sum(h@coords[,2])/length(h@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((h@coords[,1]-mean(h@coords[,1]))^2+
                (h@coords[,2]-mean(h@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(h@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Unspecified Structures and/ or Features of Undetermined Function")
points(h.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")

```

```

write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_h.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(h_1@coords[,1])/length(h_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(h_1@coords[,2])/length(h_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((h_1@coords[,1]-mean(h_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (h_1@coords[,2]-mean(h_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(h_1@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Epigraphical Site or Location")
points(h_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_h_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(h_2@coords[,1])/length(h_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(h_2@coords[,2])/length(h_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((h_2@coords[,1]-mean(h_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (h_2@coords[,2]-mean(h_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(h_2@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Find Clusters")
points(h_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_h_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(h_3@coords[,1])/length(h_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(h_3@coords[,2])/length(h_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((h_3@coords[,1]-mean(h_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (h_3@coords[,2]-mean(h_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(h_3@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
points(h_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_h_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(h_4@coords[,1])/length(h_4@coords[,1]),
           sum(h_4@coords[,2])/length(h_4@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((h_4@coords[,1]-mean(h_4@coords[,1]))^2+
                (h_4@coords[,2]-mean(h_4@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(h_4@coords[,1]))
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_4.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
points(h_4.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

```

```
table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_h_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")
```

```
mc<- cbind(sum(h_5@coords[,1])/length(h_5@coords[,1]),
           sum(h_5@coords[,2])/length(h_5@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((h_5@coords[,1]-mean(h_5@coords[,1]))^2+
                (h_5@coords[,2]-mean(h_5@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(h_5@coords[,1]))
```

```
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_5.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
points(h_5.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()
```

```
table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_h_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")
```

#Water Structures:

```
mc<- cbind(sum(i@coords[,1])/length(i@coords[,1]),
           sum(i@coords[,2])/length(i@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((i@coords[,1]-mean(i@coords[,1]))^2+
                (i@coords[,2]-mean(i@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(i@coords[,1]))
```

```
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Water Structures")
points(i.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()
```

```
table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_i.pp.csv", sep = ";")
```

```
mc<- cbind(sum(i_1@coords[,1])/length(i_1@coords[,1]),
           sum(i_1@coords[,2])/length(i_1@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((i_1@coords[,1]-mean(i_1@coords[,1]))^2+
                (i_1@coords[,2]-mean(i_1@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(i_1@coords[,1]))
```

```
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_1.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Dams/ Barrages")
points(i_1.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()
```

```
table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_i_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
```

```
mc<- cbind(sum(i_2@coords[,1])/length(i_2@coords[,1]),
           sum(i_2@coords[,2])/length(i_2@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((i_2@coords[,1]-mean(i_2@coords[,1]))^2+
                (i_2@coords[,2]-mean(i_2@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(i_2@coords[,1]))
```

```
stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_2.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Springs")
points(i_2.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
```

```

with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_i_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(i_3@coords[,1])/length(i_3@coords[,1]),
           sum(i_3@coords[,2])/length(i_3@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((i_3@coords[,1]-mean(i_3@coords[,1]))^2+
                (i_3@coords[,2]-mean(i_3@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(i_3@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_3.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Water Conduits")
points(i_3.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_i_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(i_4@coords[,1])/length(i_4@coords[,1]),
           sum(i_4@coords[,2])/length(i_4@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((i_4@coords[,1]-mean(i_4@coords[,1]))^2+
                (i_4@coords[,2]-mean(i_4@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(i_4@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_4.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Water Storage Installations")
points(i_4.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_i_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

mc<- cbind(sum(i_5@coords[,1])/length(i_5@coords[,1]),
           sum(i_5@coords[,2])/length(i_5@coords[,2])
)
stdist<- sqrt(sum((i_5@coords[,1]-mean(i_5@coords[,1]))^2+
                (i_5@coords[,2]-mean(i_5@coords[,2]))^2) /
            length(i_5@coords[,1]))

stdist
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_5.pp_MC_StDist.pdf")
plot(poly.owin, main= "Wells")
points(i_5.pp,cex=0.5, col="black", bg="grey", pch= 21)
points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
points(mc, col="black",cex= 0.75, bg="red", pch=21)
with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
library(plotrix)
draw.circle(x=mc[1],y=mc[2], radius=stdist, border="red")
dev.off()

table<- data.frame(stdist)
names (table)<- c("Standard Distance (m)")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Standard_Distance_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#####
#Global Intensities
#####
##Global Intensity= Number of points per area(km^2)
## A= a*b
area.sqm<- diff(a.pp$window$xrange) * diff(a.pp$window$yrange)
area.sqkm<- area.sqm*10^-6
#area<- area/1000000
area.sqkm
##calculate intensity

```



```

names(table)<- c("Global intensity per sqkm")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Global Intensity_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#####
##Local Intensity
#####
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=a.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Agricultural Installations");
points(a.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
#points(petra, col="black", pch=15)
#with(text(petra,labels= "Petra", pos= 3))
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_a.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Follow-up question: Does the quadratcount indicate CSR?:

## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistic

qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=a.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Agricultural Installations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(a.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=a_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Agricultural Processing Installations");
points(a_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_a_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=a_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Agricultural Processing Installations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(a_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=a_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Agricultural Storing Installations");
points(a_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_a_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=a_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Agricultural Storing Installations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(a_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=a_3.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields");
points(a_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")

```

```

write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_a_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=a_3.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(a_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=b.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Communication Infrastructures");
points(b.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_b.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=b.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Communication Infrastructures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(b.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=b_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Caravanserais");
points(b_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_b_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=b_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Caravanserais")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(b_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=b_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Road Markers");
points(b_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_b_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=b_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Road Markers")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(b_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=b_3.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Road Stations");
points(b_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")

```

```

write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_b_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=b_3.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Road Stations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(b_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=b_4.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_4.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Roads");
points(b_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_b_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=b_4.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_4.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Roads")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(b_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=b_5.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_5.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Route/ Tracks (naqb)");
points(b_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_b_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=b_5.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/b_5.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Route/ Tracks (naqb)")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(b_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=c.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/c.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites");
points(c.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_c.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=c.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/c.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(c.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=c_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/c_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations");
points(c_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_c_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

```

```
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=c_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/c_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(c_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=d.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Funerary and Commemorative Structures");
points(d.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_d.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=d.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(d.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=d_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Cemeteries");
points(d_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_d_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=d_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Cemeteries")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(d_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=d_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Isolated Funerary Monuments");
points(d_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_d_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=d_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/d_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Isolated Funerary Monuments")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(d_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=e.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Military Structures");
points(e.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_e.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
```

```

## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=e.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Military Structures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(e.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=e_1.pp)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Forts");
points(e_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_e_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=e_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Forts")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(e_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=e_2.pp)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Fortlets");
points(e_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_e_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=e_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Fortlets")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(e_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=e_3.pp)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Fortresses");
points(e_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_e_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=e_3.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Fortresses")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(e_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=e_4.pp)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_4.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Watchtowers");
points(e_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_e_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts

```

```

## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=e_4.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/e_4.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Watchtowers")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(e_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=f.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Religious Structures");
points(f.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_f.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=f.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Religious Structures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(f.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=f_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Isolated Cultic Installations");
points(f_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_f_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=f_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Isolated Cultic Installations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(f_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=f_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Sanctuaries");
points(f_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_f_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=f_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Sanctuaries")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(f_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=f_3.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures");
points(f_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_f_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics

```

```

qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=f_3.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/f_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(f_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Settlements");
points(g.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Settlements")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Cities");
points(g_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Cities")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Cluster of Building Structures");
points(g_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Cluster of Building Structures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g_3.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Farms");
points(g_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g_3.pp)

```

```

qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Farms")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g_4.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_4.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Towns");
points(g_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g_4.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_4.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Towns")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g_5.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_5.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Villae");
points(g_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g_5.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_5.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Villae")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=g_6.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_6.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Villages");
points(g_6.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_g_6.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=g_6.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/g_6.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Villages")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(g_6.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=h.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)");
points(h.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_h.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=h.pp)
qt.sites

```

```

pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)"))##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(h.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=h_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Epigraphical Sites or Locations");
points(h_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_h_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=h_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(h_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=h_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Find Clusters");
points(h_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_h_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=h_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Find Clusters")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(h_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=h_3.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Feature(s) of Undetermined Function");
points(h_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_h_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=h_3.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Feature(s) of Undetermined Function")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(h_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=h_4.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_4.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function");
points(h_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_h_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=h_4.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_4.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")

```

```
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(h_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=h_5.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_5.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function");
points(h_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_h_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=h_5.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/h_5.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(h_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=i.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Water Structures");
points(i.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_i.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=i.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Water Structures")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(i.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=i_1.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_1.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Dams/ Barrages");
points(i_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_i_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=i_1.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_1.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Dams/ Barrages")##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(i_1.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
```

```
qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=i_2.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_2.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Springs");
points(i_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_i_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=i_2.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_2.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
```

```

    for Springs"##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(i_2.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=i_3.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_3.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Water Conduits");
points(i_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_i_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=i_3.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_3.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Water Conduits"##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(i_3.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=i_4.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_4.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Water Storage Installations");
points(i_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_i_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=i_4.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_4.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Water Storage Installations"##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(i_4.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

qc.sites<-quadratcount(X=i_5.pp)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_5.pp_LIV_QC.pdf")
plot(qc.sites, main= "Local Intensities (Quadrat Counts)
      for Wells");
points(i_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()
m_qc<-mean(qc.sites) # checking the mean quadratcount
m_qc
table<- data.frame(m_qc)
names(table)<- c("Mean Quadcount")
write.table(table, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/MeanQuadcount_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")
## Chi-squared test of CSR using quadrat counts
## Pearson X2 statistics
qt.sites<-quadrat.test(X=i_5.pp)
qt.sites
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/i_5.pp_X2Test for CSR.pdf")
plot(qt.sites, main="Chi-square Test for CSR for
      for Wells"##<- zeigt statistik der local intensity
points(i_5.pp,cex=0.5, col=rgb(.2,.2,.2,.5), pch= 20)
dev.off()

#####
## Creating KDEs For Point Patterns
#####
##Agricultural Installations:
sdev_a.pp <- mean(nndist(a.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
a.pp_dens <- density(a.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_a.pp)
plot(a.pp_dens)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/a.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(a.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Agricultural Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_a.pp<- raster(a.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_a.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/a.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

sdev_a_1.pp <- mean(nndist(a_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
a_1.pp_dens <- density(a_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_a_1.pp)
plot(a_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/a_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(a_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Agricultural Processing Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_a_1.pp<- raster(a_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_a_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/a_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_a_2.pp <- mean(nndist(a_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
a_2.pp_dens <- density(a_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_a_2.pp)
plot(a_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/a_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(a_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Agricultural Storing Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_a_2.pp<- raster(a_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_a_2.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/a_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_a_3.pp <- mean(nndist(a_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
a_3.pp_dens <- density(a_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_a_3.pp)
plot(a_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/a_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(a_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_a_3.pp<- raster(a_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_a_3.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/a_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

# Communication Infrastructure:
sdev_b.pp <- mean(nndist(b.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
b.pp_dens <- density(b.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_b.pp)
plot(b.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/b.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(b.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Communication Infrastructure")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_b.pp<- raster(b.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_b.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/b.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_b_1.pp <- mean(nndist(b_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
b_1.pp_dens <- density(b_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_b_1.pp)
plot(b_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/b_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(b_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Caravanserais")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_b_1.pp<- raster(b_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_b_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/b_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_b_2.pp <- mean(nndist(b_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
b_2.pp_dens <- density(b_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_b_2.pp)
plot(b_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/b_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(b_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Road Markers")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_b_2.pp<- raster(b_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_b_2.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/b_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_b_3.pp <- mean(nndist(b_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
b_3.pp_dens <- density(b_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_b_3.pp)
plot(b_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/b_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(b_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Road Stations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_b_3.pp<- raster(b_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_b_3.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/b_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

sdev_b_4.pp <- mean(nndist(b_4.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
b_4.pp_dens <- density(b_4.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_b_4.pp)
plot(b_4.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/b_4.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(b_4.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Roads")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_b_4.pp<- raster(b_4.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_b_4.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/b_4.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_b_5.pp <- mean(nndist(b_5.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
b_5.pp_dens <- density(b_5.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_b_5.pp)
plot(b_5.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/b_5.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(b_5.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_b_5.pp<- raster(b_5.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_b_5.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/b_5.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Exploitation/ Industrial Sites
sdev_c.pp <- mean(nndist(c.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
c.pp_dens <- density(c.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_c.pp)
plot(c.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/c.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(c.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_c.pp<- raster(c.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_c.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/c.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_c_1.pp <- mean(nndist(c_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
c_1.pp_dens <- density(c_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_c_1.pp)
plot(c_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/c_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(c_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_c_1.pp<- raster(c_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_c_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/c_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
sdev_d.pp <- mean(nndist(d.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
d.pp_dens <- density(d.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_d.pp)
plot(d.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/d.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(d.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_d.pp<- raster(d.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_d.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/d.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_d_1.pp <- mean(nndist(d_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
d_1.pp_dens <- density(d_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_d_1.pp)
plot(d_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/d_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(d_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Cemeteries")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_d_1.pp<- raster(d_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_d_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/d_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_d_2.pp <- mean(nndist(d_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
d_2.pp_dens <- density(d_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_d_2.pp)
plot(d_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/d_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(d_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_d_2.pp<- raster(d_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_d_2.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/d_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Military Structures:

```

```

sdev_e.pp <- mean(nndist(e.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
e.pp_dens <- density(e.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_e.pp)
plot(e.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(e.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Military Structures")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_e.pp<- raster(e.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_e.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/e.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_e_1.pp <- mean(nndist(e_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
e_1.pp_dens <- density(e_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_e_1.pp)
plot(e_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(e_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Forts")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_e_1.pp<- raster(e_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_e_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/e_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_e_2.pp <- mean(nndist(e_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
e_2.pp_dens <- density(e_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_e_2.pp)
plot(e_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(e_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Fortlets")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_e_2.pp<- raster(e_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_e_2.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/e_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_e_3.pp <- mean(nndist(e_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
e_3.pp_dens <- density(e_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_e_3.pp)
plot(e_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(e_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Fortresses")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_e_3.pp<- raster(e_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_e_3.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/e_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_e_4.pp <- mean(nndist(e_4.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
e_4.pp_dens <- density(e_4.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_e_4.pp)
plot(e_4.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/e_4.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(e_4.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Watchtowers")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_e_4.pp<- raster(e_4.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_e_4.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/e_4.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Religious Structures:
sdev_f.pp <- mean(nndist(f.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
f.pp_dens <- density(f.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_f.pp)
plot(f.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/f.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(f.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Religious Structures")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_f.pp<- raster(f.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_f.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/f.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_f_1.pp <- mean(nndist(f_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
f_1.pp_dens <- density(f_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_f_1.pp)
plot(f_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/f_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(f_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Isolated Cultic Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_f_1.pp<- raster(f_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_f_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/f_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_f_2.pp <- mean(nndist(f_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better

```

```

f_2.pp_dens <- density(f_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_f_2.pp)
plot(f_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/f_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(f_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Sanctuaries")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_f_2.pp<- raster(f_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_f_2.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/f_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_f_3.pp <- mean(nndist(f_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
f_3.pp_dens <- density(f_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_f_3.pp)
plot(f_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/f_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(f_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_f_3.pp<- raster(f_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_f_3.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/f_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Settlements:
sdev_g.pp <- mean(nndist(g.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
g.pp_dens <- density(g.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g.pp)
plot(g.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/g.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Settlements")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g.pp<- raster(g.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/g.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_g_1.pp <- mean(nndist(g_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
g_1.pp_dens <- density(g_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g_1.pp)
plot(g_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/g_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Cities")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g_1.pp<- raster(g_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g_1.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/g_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_g_2.pp <- mean(nndist(g_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
g_2.pp_dens <- density(g_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g_2.pp)
plot(g_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/g_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Cluster of Building Structures")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g_2.pp<- raster(g_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g_2.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/g_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_g_3.pp <- mean(nndist(g_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
g_3.pp_dens <- density(g_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g_3.pp)
plot(g_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/g_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Farms")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g_3.pp<- raster(g_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g_3.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/g_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_g_4.pp <- mean(nndist(g_4.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
g_4.pp_dens <- density(g_4.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g_4.pp)
plot(g_4.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/g_4.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g_4.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Towns")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g_4.pp<- raster(g_4.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g_4.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/g_4.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_g_5.pp <- mean(nndist(g_5.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
g_5.pp_dens <- density(g_5.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g_5.pp)

```

```

plot(g_5.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/g_5.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g_5.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Villae")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g_5.pp<- raster(g_5.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g_5.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/g_5.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_g_6.pp <- mean(nndist(g_6.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
g_6.pp_dens <- density(g_6.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_g_6.pp)
plot(g_6.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/g_6.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(g_6.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Villages")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_g_6.pp<- raster(g_6.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_g_6.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/g_6.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Unspecified Structures and/or Features:
sdev_h.pp <- mean(nndist(h.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
h.pp_dens <- density(h.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_h.pp)
plot(h.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/h.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(h.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Unspecified Structure(s) and/or Feature(s)")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_h.pp<- raster(h.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_h.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/h.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_h_1.pp <- mean(nndist(h_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
h_1.pp_dens <- density(h_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_h_1.pp)
plot(h_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/h_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(h_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_h_1.pp<- raster(h_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_h_1.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/h_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_h_2.pp <- mean(nndist(h_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
h_2.pp_dens <- density(h_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_h_2.pp)
plot(h_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/h_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(h_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Find Clusters")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_h_2.pp<- raster(h_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_h_2.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/h_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_h_3.pp <- mean(nndist(h_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
h_3.pp_dens <- density(h_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_h_3.pp)
plot(h_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/h_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(h_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_h_3.pp<- raster(h_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_h_3.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/h_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_h_4.pp <- mean(nndist(h_4.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
h_4.pp_dens <- density(h_4.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_h_4.pp)
plot(h_4.pp_dens)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/h_4.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(h_4.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_h_4.pp<- raster(h_4.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_h_4.pp,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/h_4.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_h_5.pp <- mean(nndist(h_5.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is
better
h_5.pp_dens <- density(h_5.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_h_5.pp)
plot(h_5.pp_dens)

```

```

pdf("../5pictures/100AD/h_5.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(h_5.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_h_5.pp<- raster(h_5.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_h_5.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/h_5.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Water Structures:
sdev_i.pp <- mean(nndist(i.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
i.pp_dens <- density(i.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_i.pp)
plot(i.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/i.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(i.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Water Structures")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_i.pp<- raster(i.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_i.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/i.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_i_1.pp <- mean(nndist(i_1.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
i_1.pp_dens <- density(i_1.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_i_1.pp)
plot(i_1.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/i_1.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(i_1.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Dams/ Barrages")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_i_1.pp<- raster(i_1.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_i_1.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/i_1.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_i_2.pp <- mean(nndist(i_2.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
i_2.pp_dens <- density(i_2.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_i_2.pp)
plot(i_2.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/i_2.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(i_2.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Springs")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_i_2.pp<- raster(i_2.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_i_2.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/i_2.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_i_3.pp <- mean(nndist(i_3.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
i_3.pp_dens <- density(i_3.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_i_3.pp)
plot(i_3.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/i_3.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(i_3.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Water Conduits")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_i_3.pp<- raster(i_3.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_i_3.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/i_3.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_i_4.pp <- mean(nndist(i_4.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
i_4.pp_dens <- density(i_4.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_i_4.pp)
plot(i_4.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/i_4.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(i_4.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Water Storage Installations")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_i_4.pp<- raster(i_4.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_i_4.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/i_4.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

sdev_i_5.pp <- mean(nndist(i_5.pp))# although the rule of thumb is 3*mean(nndist), for this study only the mean is better
i_5.pp_dens <- density(i_5.pp, kernel="gaussian", sigma=sdev_i_5.pp)
plot(i_5.pp_dens)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/i_5.pp.pdf") # plot density as pdf
plot(i_5.pp_dens, main= "KDE of Wells")
plot(poly.owin, add=TRUE)
dev.off()
KDE_i_5.pp<- raster(i_5.pp_dens, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636")) # write Raster file of KDE
writeRaster(x = KDE_i_5.pp,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/i_5.pp_KDE.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

#####
# First Order Effects: Researching Covariates
#####

```

```

#####
library(rgdal)
##Loading covariates:
dem<- readGDAL("./3geodata/Covariates/SRTM1_Petra20km_UTM.tif")
slope<- readGDAL("./3geodata/Covariates/Slope_SRTM1_20km_Percent.tif")
geo<- readGDAL("./3geodata/Covariates/Geology.tif")
stream<-readGDAL("./3geodata/Covariates/Stream_Network_Distance_Raster_R.tif") # Distance raster from stream network
roads<-readGDAL("./3geodata/Covariates/Road_Network_Distance_Raster_R.tif") # Distance raster from road network
#####
## Researching ELEVATION dependencies:
#####
Elevation <- as.im(as.image.SpatialGridDataFrame(dem))
class(Elevation)
#Agricultural Installations:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a.pp,          # insert point pattern
                    covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
                    bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_a.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                    covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
                    bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Processing Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_a_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                    covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
                    bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Storing Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_a_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_a_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_a_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Communication Infrastructures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Communication Infrastructures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_b.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserai")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserai")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Caravanserai
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_b_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)

```

```

pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Markers
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Stations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Roads
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_b_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_b_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Exploitation/ Industrial Sites:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")

```

```

dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_c.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_c.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_c_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_c_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_d.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Funerary and Commemorative Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_d.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_d_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cemeteries
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_d_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_d_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Funerary Monuments
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_d_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Military Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Military Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_e.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Forts
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_e_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)

```

```

pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortlets
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_e_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortresses
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_e_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_e_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Watchtowers
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_e_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Religious Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_f.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Cultic Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_f_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Sanctuaries
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_f_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious/ Cultic Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_f_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious/ Cultic Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_f_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Settlement:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Settlements
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_1.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cities
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cluster of Building Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Farms
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites

```

```

plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Towns
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villae
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_6.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_g_6.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_6.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villages
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_g_6.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

# Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s):
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_h.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")

```

```

pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Epigraphical Sites or Locations
with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_h_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_2.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Find Clusters
with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_h_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_3.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_h_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_4.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Elevation, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_h_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_h_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_h_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Water Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_i.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Dams/ Barrages
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_i_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites

```

```

plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Springs
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_i_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Conduits
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_i_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Storage Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_i_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Elevation,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ELEVATION)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_KDE_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wells
      with First-Order Properties (Elevation)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Elevation_ KDE_i_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#####
## Researching STREAM dependencies:
#####
Streams <- as.im(as.image.SpatialGridDataFrame(stream))
class(Streams)

#Agricultural Installations:

```

```

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Processing Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Storing Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_3.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_a_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)

```

```

pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_a_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Communication Infrastructures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Communication Infrastructures
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_b.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserais")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserais")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Caravanserais
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_b_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Markers
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_b_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_3.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")

```

```

pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Stations
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_b_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Roads
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_b_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_b_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_b_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Exploitation/ Industrial Sites:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c.pp,          # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_c.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_c.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

```

```

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_c_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_c_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_d.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Funerary and Commemorative Structures
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_d.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_d_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cemeteries
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_d_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_d_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites

```

```

plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Funerary Monuments
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_d_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Military Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Military Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_e.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Forts
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_e_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortlets
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_e_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_3.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")

```

```

pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortresses
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_4.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Streams, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_e_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Watchtowers
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_e_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Religious Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Streams, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious Structures
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_1.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Streams, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Cultic Installations
with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,

```

```
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)
```

```
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Sanctuaries
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_3.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious/ Cultic Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_f_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious/ Cultic Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_f_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Settlement:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Settlements
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_1.pp,     # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
```

```

cov_compare <- g_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cities
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_g_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cluster of Building Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_g_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Farms
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_g_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Towns
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_g_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villae
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_g_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_6.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_g_6.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_6.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villages
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_g_6.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

# Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s):
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_h.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Epigraphical Sites or Locations
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))

```

```

writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Find Clusters
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_h_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)

```

```

cov_compare <- h_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_h_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Water Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_i.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Dams/ Barrages
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_i_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Springs
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_i_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_3.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Conduits
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_i_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Storage Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_i_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Streams,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (STREAMS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_KDE_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wells
      with First-Order Properties (Streams)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Streams_ KDE_i_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#####
## Researching GEOLOGY dependencies:
#####
Geology <- as.im(as.image.SpatialGridDataFrame(geo))
class(Geology)
#Agricultural Installations:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf

```

```

plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
      filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
      covariate = Geology,      # insert covariate raster
      bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Processing Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
      filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
      covariate = Geology,      # insert covariate raster
      bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Storing Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
      filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_3.pp,      # insert point pattern
      covariate = Geology,      # insert covariate raster
      bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_a_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
      filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_a_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Communication Infrastructures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b.pp,      # insert point pattern
      covariate = Geology,      # insert covariate raster
      bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures")

```

```

pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Communication Infrastructures
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_b.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_1.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserais")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserais")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Caravanserais
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_b_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_2.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Markers
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_b_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_3.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Stations
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,

```

```
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)
```

```
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_4.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Roads
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_5.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_b_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_b_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Exploitation/ Industrial Sites:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_c.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_c.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_c_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
```

```

plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_c_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_d.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Funerary and Commemorative Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_d.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_d_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cemeteries
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_d_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_d_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Funerary Monuments
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_d_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Military Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e.pp,      # insert point pattern
                  covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                  bw = 100
)

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Military Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_e.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_1.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Forts
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_e_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortlets
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_e_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortresses
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,

```

```
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)
```

```
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_4.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_e_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Watchtowers
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_e_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Religious Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_f.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_1.pp,    # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Cultic Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_f_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_2.pp,    # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
```

```

cov_compare <- f_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Sanctuaries
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_f_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious/ Cultic Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_f_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious/ Cultic Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_f_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Settlement:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Settlements
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cities
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)

```

```

)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cluster of Building Structures
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_3.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Farms
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_4.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Towns
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_5.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villae
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))

```

```

writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_6.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_g_6.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_6.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villages
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_g_6.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

# Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s):
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_h.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Epigraphical Sites or Locations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_h_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)

```

```

pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Find Clusters
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_3.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_4.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_5.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_h_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_h_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Water Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)

```

```

)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Structures
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_i.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_1.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Dams/ Barrages
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_i_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_2.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Springs
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_ KDE_i_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_3.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Geology, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Conduits
with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))

```

```

writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100)
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Storage Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Geology,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100)
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (GEOLOGY)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wells
      with First-Order Properties (Geology)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Geology_KDE_i_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#####
## Researching ROADS dependencies:
#####
Roads <- as.im(as.image.SpatialGridDataFrame(roads))
class(Roads)
#Agricultural Installations:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100)
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_a.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_1.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100)
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Processing Installations
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_a_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads,    # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Storing Installations
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_a_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = a_3.pp,      # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads,    # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_a_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- a_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_a_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Communication Infrastructures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b.pp,      # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads,    # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Communication Infrastructures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Communication Infrastructures
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,

```

```
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)
```

```
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserais")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Caravanserais")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Caravanserais
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Markers")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Markers
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_3.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Road Stations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Road Stations
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_4.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Roads")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
```

```

cov_compare <- b_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Roads
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_b_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = b_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_b_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- b_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_b_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Exploitation/ Industrial Sites:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_c.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_c.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = c_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Industrial/ Exploitation Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_c_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- c_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_c_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Funerary and Commemorative Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_d.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Funerary and Commemorative Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_d.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_1.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cemeteries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_d_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cemeteries
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_d_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = d_2.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,    # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Funerary Monuments ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_d_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- d_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Funerary Monuments
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_d_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Military Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,  # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Military Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Military Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))

```

```

writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_1.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Forts")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Forts
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortlets")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortlets
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Fortresses")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- e_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Fortresses
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = e_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Watchtowers ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_e_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)

```

```

cov_compare <- e_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Watchtowers
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_e_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Religious Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_f.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_1.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Isolated Cultic Installations ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Isolated Cultic Installations
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_f_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_2.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Sanctuaries
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_f_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = f_3.pp,        # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,     # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)

```

```

plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Religious/ Cultic Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_f_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- f_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Religious/ Cultic Structures
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_f_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Settlement:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Settlements")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Settlements
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_1.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cities")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cities
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_2.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Cluster of Building Structures
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()

```

```

FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Farms")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Farms
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Towns")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Towns
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_5.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villae")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villae
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = g_6.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Villages")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_g_6.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)

```

```

pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- g_6.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Villages
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_g_6.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

# Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s):
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_h.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_1.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Epigraphical Sites or Locations
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_h_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_2.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Find Clusters")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Find Clusters
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_h_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_3.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100

```

```

)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_h_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_4.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_h_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = h_5.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_h_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- h_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_h_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#Water Structures:
cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i.pp,      # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,   # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Structures ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Structures
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()

```

```

FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_1.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Dams/ Barrages ")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_1.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_1.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Dams/ Barrages
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_1.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_2.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Springs")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_2.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_2.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Springs
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_2.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_3.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Conduits")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_3.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_3.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Conduits
      with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
            filename="./4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_3.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_4.pp,          # insert point pattern
                   covariate = Roads,      # insert covariate raster
                   bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_4.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)

```

```

pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_4.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Water Storage Installations
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_i_4.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

cov_sites <- rhohat(object = i_5.pp, # insert point pattern
covariate = Roads, # insert covariate raster
bw = 100
)
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white") # plot cov_sites as pdf
plot(cov_sites, main= "First-Order Properties for Wells")
dev.off()
write.table(cov_sites, file="../4result/Tables/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_i_5.pp.csv", sep = ";")

#Kernel Density Estimation First Order with Covariate (ROADS)
pred_cov_sites <- predict(cov_sites)
cov_compare <- i_5.pp_dens- pred_cov_sites
plot(cov_compare)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_KDE_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=8, bg="white")# plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(cov_compare, main= "KDE of Wells
with First-Order Properties (Roads)")
dev.off()
FirstO_K<- raster(cov_compare, crs= CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = FirstO_K,
filename="../4result/Raster/100AD/1stOrder_Roads_ KDE_i_5.pp.tif", overwrite=TRUE)

#####
#####PEARSON CORRELATION TESTS#####
#####
#####
#####
## Creating Random Sampling Points for Comparison
##("The points where we compare the values should not be the monuments
## or villages locations, because this could produce a bias.
##Hence we use random sampling points"
##- Nakoinz - Knitter, Modelling Human Behaviour in Landscapes, 2016, pp. 132)
#####

samppt <- spsample(poly.owin, 500, type="random")

library(mapttools)

sgdf_a.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(a.pp_dens)
a.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_a.pp_dens, x=samppt)
a.pp_dens_samp2<- a.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_a_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(a_1.pp_dens)
a_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_a_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
a_1.pp_dens_samp2<- a_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_a_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(a_2.pp_dens)
a_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_a_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
a_2.pp_dens_samp2<- a_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_a_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(a_3.pp_dens)
a_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_a_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
a_3.pp_dens_samp2<- a_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_b.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(b.pp_dens)
b.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_b.pp_dens, x=samppt)
b.pp_dens_samp2<- b.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_b_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(b_1.pp_dens)
b_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_b_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
b_1.pp_dens_samp2<- b_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_b_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(b_2.pp_dens)
b_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_b_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
b_2.pp_dens_samp2<- b_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_b_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(b_3.pp_dens)
b_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_b_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
b_3.pp_dens_samp2<- b_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_b_4.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(b_4.pp_dens)
b_4.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_b_4.pp_dens, x=samppt)
b_4.pp_dens_samp2<- b_4.pp_dens_samp[,1]

```

```
sgdf_b_5.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(b_5.pp_dens)
b_5.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_b_5.pp_dens, x=samppt)
b_5.pp_dens_samp2<- b_5.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_c.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(c.pp_dens)
c.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_c.pp_dens, x=samppt)
c.pp_dens_samp2<- c.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_c_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(c_1.pp_dens)
c_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_c_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
c_1.pp_dens_samp2<- c_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_d.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(d.pp_dens)
d.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_d.pp_dens, x=samppt)
d.pp_dens_samp2<- d.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_d_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(d_1.pp_dens)
d_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_d_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
d_1.pp_dens_samp2<- d_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_d_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(d_2.pp_dens)
d_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_d_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
d_2.pp_dens_samp2<- d_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_e.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(e.pp_dens)
e.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_e.pp_dens, x=samppt)
e.pp_dens_samp2<- e.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_e_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(e_1.pp_dens)
e_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_e_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
e_1.pp_dens_samp2<- e_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_e_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(e_2.pp_dens)
e_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_e_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
e_2.pp_dens_samp2<- e_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_e_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(e_3.pp_dens)
e_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_e_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
e_3.pp_dens_samp2<- e_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_e_4.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(e_4.pp_dens)
e_4.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_e_4.pp_dens, x=samppt)
e_4.pp_dens_samp2<- e_4.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_f.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(f.pp_dens)
f.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_f.pp_dens, x=samppt)
f.pp_dens_samp2<- f.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_f_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(f_1.pp_dens)
f_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_f_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
f_1.pp_dens_samp2<- f_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_f_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(f_2.pp_dens)
f_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_f_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
f_2.pp_dens_samp2<- f_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_f_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(f_3.pp_dens)
f_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_f_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
f_3.pp_dens_samp2<- f_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_g.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g.pp_dens)
g.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g.pp_dens_samp2<- g.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_g_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g_1.pp_dens)
g_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g_1.pp_dens_samp2<- g_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_g_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g_2.pp_dens)
g_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g_2.pp_dens_samp2<- g_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_g_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g_3.pp_dens)
g_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g_3.pp_dens_samp2<- g_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_g_4.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g_4.pp_dens)
g_4.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g_4.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g_4.pp_dens_samp2<- g_4.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_g_5.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g_5.pp_dens)
g_5.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g_5.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g_5.pp_dens_samp2<- g_5.pp_dens_samp[,1]
```

```

sgdf_g_6.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(g_6.pp_dens)
g_6.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_g_6.pp_dens, x=samppt)
g_6.pp_dens_samp2<- g_6.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_h.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(h.pp_dens)
h.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_h.pp_dens, x=samppt)
h.pp_dens_samp2<- h.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_h_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(h_1.pp_dens)
h_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_h_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
h_1.pp_dens_samp2<- h_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_h_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(h_2.pp_dens)
h_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_h_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
h_2.pp_dens_samp2<- h_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_h_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(h_3.pp_dens)
h_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_h_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
h_3.pp_dens_samp2<- h_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_h_4.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(h_4.pp_dens)
h_4.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_h_4.pp_dens, x=samppt)
h_4.pp_dens_samp2<- h_4.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_h_5.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(h_5.pp_dens)
h_5.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_h_5.pp_dens, x=samppt)
h_5.pp_dens_samp2<- h_5.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_i.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(i.pp_dens)
i.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_i.pp_dens, x=samppt)
i.pp_dens_samp2<- i.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_i_1.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(i_1.pp_dens)
i_1.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_i_1.pp_dens, x=samppt)
i_1.pp_dens_samp2<- i_1.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_i_2.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(i_2.pp_dens)
i_2.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_i_2.pp_dens, x=samppt)
i_2.pp_dens_samp2<- i_2.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_i_3.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(i_3.pp_dens)
i_3.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_i_3.pp_dens, x=samppt)
i_3.pp_dens_samp2<- i_3.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_i_4.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(i_4.pp_dens)
i_4.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_i_4.pp_dens, x=samppt)
i_4.pp_dens_samp2<- i_4.pp_dens_samp[,1]

sgdf_i_5.pp_dens <- as.SpatialGridDataFrame.im(i_5.pp_dens)
i_5.pp_dens_samp <- over(y=sgdf_i_5.pp_dens, x=samppt)
i_5.pp_dens_samp2<- i_5.pp_dens_samp[,1]

##### !!!!!!! with Elevation and other covariates?!?!?!#####

#####
##=====
## Pearson Correlation Test (WITH 500 SAMPLE POINTS)
#####
## From a.pp (Agricultural Installations):
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, a_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2a_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, a_2.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2a_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, a_3.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2a_3.pp.txt")

PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, b.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2b.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, b_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2b_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, b_2.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2b_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, b_3.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2b_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, b_4.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2b_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, b_5.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2b_5.pp.txt")

PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, c.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_a.pp2c.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens_samp2, c_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")

```



```
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2f.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, f_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2f_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, f_2.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2f_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, f_3.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2f_3.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, g.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2g.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, g_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2g_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, g_2.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2g_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, g_3.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2g_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, g_4.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2g_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, g_5.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2g_5.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(g_6.pp_dens_samp2, i_5.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_g_6.pp2i_5.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, h.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2h.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, h_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2h_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, h_2.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2h_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, h_3.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2h_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, h_4.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2h_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, h_5.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2h_5.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, i.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2i.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, i_1.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2i_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, i_2.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2i_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, i_3.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2i_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, i_4.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2i_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens_samp2, i_5.pp_dens_samp2, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_SAMP_i_5.pp2i_5.pp.txt")
```

```
#####
#####
## Pearson Correlation Test (WITH ACTUAL LOCATION (Densities) of Patterns)
#####
# creating vectors to enable Pearson correlation test for the actual patterns (without sample points):
a.pp_dens2<- data.frame(a.pp_dens)
a.pp_dens3<- a.pp_dens2[,3]

a_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(a_1.pp_dens)
a_1.pp_dens3<- a_1.pp_dens2[,3]

a_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(a_2.pp_dens)
a_2.pp_dens3<- a_2.pp_dens2[,3]

a_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(a_3.pp_dens)
a_3.pp_dens3<- a_3.pp_dens2[,3]

b.pp_dens2<- data.frame(b.pp_dens)
b.pp_dens3<- b.pp_dens2[,3]

b_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(b_1.pp_dens)
b_1.pp_dens3<- b_1.pp_dens2[,3]

b_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(b_2.pp_dens)
b_2.pp_dens3<- b_2.pp_dens2[,3]

b_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(b_3.pp_dens)
b_3.pp_dens3<- b_3.pp_dens2[,3]

b_4.pp_dens2<- data.frame(b_4.pp_dens)
b_4.pp_dens3<- b_4.pp_dens2[,3]

b_5.pp_dens2<- data.frame(b_5.pp_dens)
b_5.pp_dens3<- b_5.pp_dens2[,3]
```

```
c.pp_dens2<- data.frame(c.pp_dens)
c.pp_dens3<- c.pp_dens2[,3]

c_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(c_1.pp_dens)
c_1.pp_dens3<- c_1.pp_dens2[,3]

d.pp_dens2<- data.frame(d.pp_dens)
d.pp_dens3<- d.pp_dens2[,3]

d_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(d_1.pp_dens)
d_1.pp_dens3<- d_1.pp_dens2[,3]

d_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(d_2.pp_dens)
d_2.pp_dens3<- d_2.pp_dens2[,3]

e.pp_dens2<- data.frame(e.pp_dens)
e.pp_dens3<- e.pp_dens2[,3]

e_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(e_1.pp_dens)
e_1.pp_dens3<- e_1.pp_dens2[,3]

e_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(e_2.pp_dens)
e_2.pp_dens3<- e_2.pp_dens2[,3]

e_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(e_3.pp_dens)
e_3.pp_dens3<- e_3.pp_dens2[,3]

e_4.pp_dens2<- data.frame(e_4.pp_dens)
e_4.pp_dens3<- e_4.pp_dens2[,3]

f.pp_dens2<- data.frame(f.pp_dens)
f.pp_dens3<- f.pp_dens2[,3]

f_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(f_1.pp_dens)
f_1.pp_dens3<- f_1.pp_dens2[,3]

f_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(f_2.pp_dens)
f_2.pp_dens3<- f_2.pp_dens2[,3]

f_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(f_3.pp_dens)
f_3.pp_dens3<- f_3.pp_dens2[,3]

g.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g.pp_dens)
g.pp_dens3<- g.pp_dens2[,3]

g_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g_1.pp_dens)
g_1.pp_dens3<- g_1.pp_dens2[,3]

g_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g_2.pp_dens)
g_2.pp_dens3<- g_2.pp_dens2[,3]

g_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g_3.pp_dens)
g_3.pp_dens3<- g_3.pp_dens2[,3]

g_4.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g_4.pp_dens)
g_4.pp_dens3<- g_4.pp_dens2[,3]

g_5.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g_5.pp_dens)
g_5.pp_dens3<- g_5.pp_dens2[,3]

g_6.pp_dens2<- data.frame(g_6.pp_dens)
g_6.pp_dens3<- g_6.pp_dens2[,3]

h.pp_dens2<- data.frame(h.pp_dens)
h.pp_dens3<- h.pp_dens2[,3]

h_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(h_1.pp_dens)
h_1.pp_dens3<- h_1.pp_dens2[,3]

h_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(h_2.pp_dens)
h_2.pp_dens3<- h_2.pp_dens2[,3]

h_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(h_3.pp_dens)
h_3.pp_dens3<- h_3.pp_dens2[,3]

h_4.pp_dens2<- data.frame(h_4.pp_dens)
h_4.pp_dens3<- h_4.pp_dens2[,3]

h_5.pp_dens2<- data.frame(h_5.pp_dens)
h_5.pp_dens3<- h_5.pp_dens2[,3]

i.pp_dens2<- data.frame(i.pp_dens)
i.pp_dens3<- i.pp_dens2[,3]
```

```
i_1.pp_dens2<- data.frame(i_1.pp_dens)
i_1.pp_dens3<- i_1.pp_dens2[,3]

i_2.pp_dens2<- data.frame(i_2.pp_dens)
i_2.pp_dens3<- i_2.pp_dens2[,3]

i_3.pp_dens2<- data.frame(i_3.pp_dens)
i_3.pp_dens3<- i_3.pp_dens2[,3]

i_4.pp_dens2<- data.frame(i_4.pp_dens)
i_4.pp_dens3<- i_4.pp_dens2[,3]

i_5.pp_dens2<- data.frame(i_5.pp_dens)
i_5.pp_dens3<- i_5.pp_dens2[,3]
```

```
#####
## Actual Pearson Correlation test for the actual patterns (without sample points):
#####
```

```
## From a.pp (Agricultural Installations):
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, a_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2a_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, a_2.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2a_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, a_3.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2a_3.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, b.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2b.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, b_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2b_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, b_2.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2b_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, b_3.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2b_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, b_4.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2b_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, b_5.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2b_5.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, c.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2c.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, c_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2c_1.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, d.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2d.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, d_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2d_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, d_2.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2d_2.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, e.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2e.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, e_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2e_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, e_2.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2e_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, e_3.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2e_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, e_4.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2e_4.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, f.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2f.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, f_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2f_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, f_2.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2f_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, f_3.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2f_3.pp.txt")
```

```
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, g.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2g.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, g_1.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2g_1.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, g_2.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2g_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, g_3.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2g_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, g_4.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2g_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(a.pp_dens3, g_5.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_a.pp2g_5.pp.txt")
```



```
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_i_5.pp2i_2.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens3, i_3.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_i_5.pp2i_3.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens3, i_4.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_i_5.pp2i_4.pp.txt")
PC_test<-cor.test(i_5.pp_dens3, i_5.pp_dens3, method="p")
capture.output(PC_test, file = "./4result/TXTs/100AD/PC_test_i_5.pp2i_5.pp.txt")
```

```
#####
## Raster extraction:
#####
slope2<- raster("./3geodata/Covariates/Slope_SRTM1_20km_Percent.tif")
geo2<- raster("./3geodata/Covariates/Geo_Reclass_PPA.tif")
aspect<- raster("./3geodata/Covariates/SRTM1_Slope Aspect.tif")
dem2<-raster("./3geodata/Covariates/SRTM1_Petra20km_UTM.tif")
streams2<- raster("./3geodata/Covariates/Stream_Network_Distance_Raster_R.tif")
roads2<- raster("./3geodata/Covariates/Road_Network_Distance_Raster_R.tif")
```

```
# Agricultural Installations:
a_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(a),
                             a$Site_Name,
                             extract(slope2, a),
                             extract(geo2,a),
                             extract(aspect,a),
                             extract(dem2,a),
                             extract(streams2,a),
                             extract(roads2,a))
names(a_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                          "Slope Value (%)",
                          "Geology Cost Classes",
                          "Slope Aspect Values",
                          "Elevation (m)",
                          "Distance to Streams (m)",
                          "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(a_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_a.xlsx")
```

```
a_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(a_1),
                               a_1$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, a_1),
                               extract(geo2,a_1),
                               extract(aspect,a_1),
                               extract(dem2,a_1),
                               extract(streams2,a_1),
                               extract(roads2,a_1))
names(a_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
                            "Distance to Streams (m)",
                            "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(a_1_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_a_1.xlsx")
```

```
a_2_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(a_2),
                               a_2$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, a_2),
                               extract(geo2,a_2),
                               extract(aspect,a_2),
                               extract(dem2,a_2),
                               extract(streams2,a_2),
                               extract(roads2,a_2))
names(a_2_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
                            "Distance to Streams (m)",
                            "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(a_2_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_a_2.xlsx")
```

```
a_3_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(a_3),
                               a_3$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, a_3),
                               extract(geo2,a_3),
                               extract(aspect,a_3),
                               extract(dem2,a_3),
                               extract(streams2,a_3),
                               extract(roads2,a_3))
names(a_3_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
```

```
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(a_3_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_a_3.xlsx")
```

```
b_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(b),
                             b$Site_Name,
                             extract(slope2, b),
                             extract(geo2,b),
                             extract(aspect,b),
                             extract(dem2,b),
                             extract(streams2,b),
                             extract(roads2,b))
names(b_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                          "Slope Value (%)",
                          "Geology Cost Classes",
                          "Slope Aspect Values",
                          "Elevation (m)",
                          "Distance to Streams (m)",
                          "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(b_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_b.xlsx")
```

```
b_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(b_1),
                               b_1$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, b_1),
                               extract(geo2,b_1),
                               extract(aspect,b_1),
                               extract(dem2,b_1),
                               extract(streams2,b_1),
                               extract(roads2,b_1))
names(b_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
                            "Distance to Streams (m)",
                            "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(b_1_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_b_1.xlsx")
```

```
b_2_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(b_2),
                               b_2$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, b_2),
                               extract(geo2,b_2),
                               extract(aspect,b_2),
                               extract(dem2,b_2),
                               extract(streams2,b_2),
                               extract(roads2,b_2))
names(b_2_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
                            "Distance to Streams (m)",
                            "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(b_2_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_b_2.xlsx")
```

```
b_3_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(b_3),
                               b_3$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, b_3),
                               extract(geo2,b_3),
                               extract(aspect,b_3),
                               extract(dem2,b_3),
                               extract(streams2,b_3),
                               extract(roads2,b_3))
names(b_3_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
                            "Distance to Streams (m)",
                            "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(b_3_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_b_3.xlsx")
```

```
b_4_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(b_4),
                               b_4$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, b_4),
                               extract(geo2,b_4),
                               extract(aspect,b_4),
                               extract(dem2,b_4),
                               extract(streams2,b_4),
                               extract(roads2,b_4))
names(b_4_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                            "Slope Value (%)",
                            "Geology Cost Classes",
                            "Slope Aspect Values",
                            "Elevation (m)",
```

```
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(b_4_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_b_4.xlsx")
```

```
b_5_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(b_5),
                               b_5$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, b_5),
                               extract(geo2,b_5),
                               extract(aspect,b_5),
                               extract(dem2,b_5),
                               extract(streams2,b_5),
                               extract(roads2,b_5))
names(b_5_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(b_5_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_b_5.xlsx")
```

```
c_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(c),
                              c$Site_Name,
                              extract(slope2, c),
                              extract(geo2,c),
                              extract(aspect,c),
                              extract(dem2,c),
                              extract(streams2,c),
                              extract(roads2,c))
names(c_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                           "Slope Value (%)",
                           "Geology Cost Classes",
                           "Slope Aspect Values",
                           "Elevation (m)",
                           "Distance to Streams (m)",
                           "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(c_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_c.xlsx")
```

```
c_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(c_1),
                                c_1$Site_Name,
                                extract(slope2, c_1),
                                extract(geo2,c_1),
                                extract(aspect,c_1),
                                extract(dem2,c_1),
                                extract(streams2,c_1),
                                extract(roads2,c_1))
names(c_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(c_1_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_c_1.xlsx")
```

```
d_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(d),
                              d$Site_Name,
                              extract(slope2, d),
                              extract(geo2,d),
                              extract(aspect,d),
                              extract(dem2,d),
                              extract(streams2,d),
                              extract(roads2,d))
names(d_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                           "Slope Value (%)",
                           "Geology Cost Classes",
                           "Slope Aspect Values",
                           "Elevation (m)",
                           "Distance to Streams (m)",
                           "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(d_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_d.xlsx")
```

```
d_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(d_1),
                                d_1$Site_Name,
                                extract(slope2, d_1),
                                extract(geo2,d_1),
                                extract(aspect,d_1),
                                extract(dem2,d_1),
                                extract(streams2,d_1),
                                extract(roads2,d_1))
names(d_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
```

```

        "Slope Aspect Values",
        "Elevation (m)",
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(d_1_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_d_1.xlsx")

d_2_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(d_2),
                               d_2$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, d_2),
                               extract(geo2,d_2),
                               extract(aspect,d_2),
                               extract(dem2,d_2),
                               extract(streams2,d_2),
                               extract(roads2,d_2))
names(d_2_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(d_2_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_d_2.xlsx")

e_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(e),
                              e$Site_Name,
                              extract(slope2, e),
                              extract(geo2,e),
                              extract(aspect,e),
                              extract(dem2,e),
                              extract(streams2,e),
                              extract(roads2,e))
names(e_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                          "Slope Value (%)",
                          "Geology Cost Classes",
                          "Slope Aspect Values",
                          "Elevation (m)",
                          "Distance to Streams (m)",
                          "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(e_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_e.xlsx")

e_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(e_1),
                               e_1$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, e_1),
                               extract(geo2,e_1),
                               extract(aspect,e_1),
                               extract(dem2,e_1),
                               extract(streams2,e_1),
                               extract(roads2,e_1))
names(e_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(e_1_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_e_1.xlsx")

e_2_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(e_2),
                               e_2$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, e_2),
                               extract(geo2,e_2),
                               extract(aspect,e_2),
                               extract(dem2,e_2),
                               extract(streams2,e_2),
                               extract(roads2,e_2))
names(e_2_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(e_2_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_e_2.xlsx")

e_3_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(e_3),
                               e_3$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, e_3),
                               extract(geo2,e_3),
                               extract(aspect,e_3),
                               extract(dem2,e_3),
                               extract(streams2,e_3),
                               extract(roads2,e_3))
names(e_3_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",

```



```

names(f_3_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(f_3_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_f_3.xlsx")

g_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g),
                             g$Site_Name,
                             extract(slope2, g),
                             extract(geo2,g),
                             extract(aspect,g),
                             extract(dem2,g),
                             extract(streams2,g),
                             extract(roads2,g))
names(g_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                           "Slope Value (%)",
                           "Geology Cost Classes",
                           "Slope Aspect Values",
                           "Elevation (m)",
                           "Distance to Streams (m)",
                           "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g.xlsx")

g_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g_1),
                               g_1$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, g_1),
                               extract(geo2,g_1),
                               extract(aspect,g_1),
                               extract(dem2,g_1),
                               extract(streams2,g_1),
                               extract(roads2,g_1))
names(g_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                              "Slope Value (%)",
                              "Geology Cost Classes",
                              "Slope Aspect Values",
                              "Elevation (m)",
                              "Distance to Streams (m)",
                              "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_1_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g_1.xlsx")

g_2_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g_2),
                               g_2$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, g_2),
                               extract(geo2,g_2),
                               extract(aspect,g_2),
                               extract(dem2,g_2),
                               extract(streams2,g_2),
                               extract(roads2,g_2))
names(g_2_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                              "Slope Value (%)",
                              "Geology Cost Classes",
                              "Slope Aspect Values",
                              "Elevation (m)",
                              "Distance to Streams (m)",
                              "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_2_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g_2.xlsx")

g_3_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g_3),
                               g_3$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, g_3),
                               extract(geo2,g_3),
                               extract(aspect,g_3),
                               extract(dem2,g_3),
                               extract(streams2,g_3),
                               extract(roads2,g_3))
names(g_3_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                              "Slope Value (%)",
                              "Geology Cost Classes",
                              "Slope Aspect Values",
                              "Elevation (m)",
                              "Distance to Streams (m)",
                              "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_3_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g_3.xlsx")

g_4_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g_4),
                               g_4$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, g_4),
                               extract(geo2,g_4),
                               extract(aspect,g_4),
                               extract(dem2,g_4),
                               extract(streams2,g_4),
                               extract(roads2,g_4))

```

```

names(g_4_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_4_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g_4.xlsx")

g_5_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g_5),
                               g_5$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, g_5),
                               extract(geo2, g_5),
                               extract(aspect, g_5),
                               extract(dem2, g_5),
                               extract(streams2, g_5),
                               extract(roads2, g_5))
names(g_5_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_5_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g_5.xlsx")

g_6_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(g_6),
                               g_6$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, g_6),
                               extract(geo2, g_6),
                               extract(aspect, g_6),
                               extract(dem2, g_6),
                               extract(streams2, g_6),
                               extract(roads2, g_6))
names(g_6_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(g_6_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_g_6.xlsx")

h_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(h),
                              h$Site_Name,
                              extract(slope2, h),
                              extract(geo2, h),
                              extract(aspect, h),
                              extract(dem2, h),
                              extract(streams2, h),
                              extract(roads2, h))
names(h_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                           "Slope Value (%)",
                           "Geology Cost Classes",
                           "Slope Aspect Values",
                           "Elevation (m)",
                           "Distance to Streams (m)",
                           "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(h_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_h.xlsx")

h_1_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(h_1),
                               h_1$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, h_1),
                               extract(geo2, h_1),
                               extract(aspect, h_1),
                               extract(dem2, h_1),
                               extract(streams2, h_1),
                               extract(roads2, h_1))
names(h_1_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
                             "Slope Value (%)",
                             "Geology Cost Classes",
                             "Slope Aspect Values",
                             "Elevation (m)",
                             "Distance to Streams (m)",
                             "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(h_1_rast_extract, file=".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Landscape Infos_h_1.xlsx")

h_2_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(h_2),
                               h_2$Site_Name,
                               extract(slope2, h_2),
                               extract(geo2, h_2),
                               extract(aspect, h_2),
                               extract(dem2, h_2),
                               extract(streams2, h_2),
                               extract(roads2, h_2))

```



```

        extract(roads2,i_2))
names(i_2_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
        "Slope Value (%)",
        "Geology Cost Classes",
        "Slope Aspect Values",
        "Elevation (m)",
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(i_2_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_i_2.xlsx")

```

```

i_3_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(i_3),
        i_3$Site_Name,
        extract(slope2, i_3),
        extract(geo2,i_3),
        extract(aspect,i_3),
        extract(dem2,i_3),
        extract(streams2,i_3),
        extract(roads2,i_3))
names(i_3_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
        "Slope Value (%)",
        "Geology Cost Classes",
        "Slope Aspect Values",
        "Elevation (m)",
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(i_3_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_i_3.xlsx")

```

```

i_4_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(i_4),
        i_4$Site_Name,
        extract(slope2, i_4),
        extract(geo2,i_4),
        extract(aspect,i_4),
        extract(dem2,i_4),
        extract(streams2,i_4),
        extract(roads2,i_4))
names(i_4_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
        "Slope Value (%)",
        "Geology Cost Classes",
        "Slope Aspect Values",
        "Elevation (m)",
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(i_4_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_i_4.xlsx")

```

```

i_5_rast_extract <- data.frame(coordinates(i_5),
        i_5$Site_Name,
        extract(slope2, i_5),
        extract(geo2,i_5),
        extract(aspect,i_5),
        extract(dem2,i_5),
        extract(streams2,i_5),
        extract(roads2,i_5))
names(i_5_rast_extract) <- c("x", "y", "Site Name",
        "Slope Value (%)",
        "Geology Cost Classes",
        "Slope Aspect Values",
        "Elevation (m)",
        "Distance to Streams (m)",
        "Distance to Roads (m)")
write.xlsx(i_5_rast_extract, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Landscape Infos_i_5.xlsx")

```

```

#####
## Extracting Euclidean Distances between Arch Evidence (and SubCats)-Types:
#####

```

```

##Archaeological Evidence:
ArchEv_dist1<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,b.pp)),
min(crossdist(a.pp,b.pp)),
max(crossdist(a.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist1) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist1)<- "Between a.pp and b.pp"

```

```

ArchEv_dist2<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,c.pp)),
min(crossdist(a.pp,c.pp)),
max(crossdist(a.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist2) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist2)<- "Between a.pp and c.pp"

```

```

ArchEv_dist3<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,d.pp)),
        min(crossdist(a.pp,d.pp)),

```

```

        max(crossdist(a.pp,d.pp))
names(ArchEv_dist3) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist3)<- "Between a.pp and d.pp"

ArchEv_dist4<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,e.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a.pp,e.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist4) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist4)<- "Between a.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist5<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,f.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a.pp,f.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist5) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist5)<- "Between a.pp and f.pp"

ArchEv_dist6<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,g.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a.pp,g.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist6) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist6)<- "Between a.pp and g.pp"

ArchEv_dist7<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,h.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a.pp,h.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist7) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist7)<- "Between a.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist8<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(a.pp,i.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a.pp,i.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist8) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist8)<- "Between a.pp and i.pp"

ArchEv_dist9<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,a.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,a.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist9) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist9)<- "Between b.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist10<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,c.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,c.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist10) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist10)<- "Between b.pp and c.pp"

ArchEv_dist11<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,d.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,d.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist11) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist11)<- "Between b.pp and d.pp"

ArchEv_dist12<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,e.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,e.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist12) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist12)<- "Between b.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist13<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,f.pp)),

```

```

                min(crossdist(b.pp,f.pp)),
                max(crossdist(b.pp,f.pp))
names(ArchEv_dist13) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist13)<- "Between b.pp and f.pp"

ArchEv_dist14<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,g.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,g.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist14) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist14)<- "Between b.pp and g.pp"

ArchEv_dist15<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,h.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,h.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist15) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist15)<- "Between b.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist16<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(b.pp,i.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(b.pp,i.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(b.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist16) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist16)<- "Between b.pp and i.pp"

ArchEv_dist17<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,a.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c.pp,a.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist17) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist17)<- "Between c.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist18<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,b.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c.pp,b.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist18) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist18)<- "Between c.pp and b.pp"

ArchEv_dist19<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,d.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c.pp,d.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist19) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist19)<- "Between c.pp and d.pp"

ArchEv_dist20<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,e.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c.pp,e.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist20) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist20)<- "Between c.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist21<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,f.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c.pp,f.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist21) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist21)<- "Between c.pp and f.pp"

ArchEv_dist22<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,g.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c.pp,g.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist22) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist22)<- "Between c.pp and g.pp"

```

```

ArchEv_dist23<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,h.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(c.pp,h.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(c.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist23) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist23)<- "Between c.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist24<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(c.pp,i.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(c.pp,i.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(c.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist24) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist24)<- "Between c.pp and i.pp"

ArchEv_dist25<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,a.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d.pp,a.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist25) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist25)<- "Between d.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist26<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,b.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,b.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist26) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist26)<- "Between d.pp and b.pp"

ArchEv_dist27<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,c.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,c.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist27) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist27)<- "Between d.pp and c.pp"

ArchEv_dist28<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,e.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,e.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist28) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist28)<- "Between d.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist29<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,f.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,f.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist29) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist29)<- "Between d.pp and f.pp"

ArchEv_dist30<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,g.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,g.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist30) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist30)<- "Between d.pp and g.pp"

ArchEv_dist31<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,h.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,h.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist31) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist31)<- "Between d.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist32<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(d.pp,i.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(d.pp,i.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(d.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist32) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist32)<- "Between d.pp and i.pp"

```

```

ArchEv_dist33<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,a.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,a.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist33) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist33)<- "Between e.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist34<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,b.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,b.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist34) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist34)<- "Between e.pp and b.pp"

ArchEv_dist35<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,c.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,c.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist35) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist35)<- "Between e.pp and c.pp"

ArchEv_dist36<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,d.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,d.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist36) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist36)<- "Between e.pp and d.pp"

ArchEv_dist37<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,f.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,f.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist37) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist37)<- "Between e.pp and f.pp"

ArchEv_dist38<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,g.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,g.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist38) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist38)<- "Between e.pp and g.pp"

ArchEv_dist39<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,h.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,h.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist39) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist39)<- "Between e.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist40<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(e.pp,i.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(e.pp,i.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(e.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist40) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist40)<- "Between e.pp and i.pp"

ArchEv_dist41<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,a.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(f.pp,a.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(f.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist41) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist41)<- "Between f.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist42<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,b.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(f.pp,b.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(f.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist42) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist42)<- "Between f.pp and b.pp"

ArchEv_dist43<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,c.pp)),

```

```

                min(crossdist(f.pp,c.pp)),
                max(crossdist(f.pp,c.pp))
names(ArchEv_dist43) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist43)<- "Between f.pp and c.pp"

ArchEv_dist44<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,d.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(f.pp,d.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(f.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist44) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist44)<- "Between f.pp and d.pp"

ArchEv_dist45<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,e.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(f.pp,e.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(f.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist45) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist45)<- "Between f.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist46<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,g.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(f.pp,g.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(f.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist46) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist46)<- "Between f.pp and g.pp"

ArchEv_dist47<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,h.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(f.pp,h.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(f.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist47) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist47)<- "Between f.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist48<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(f.pp,i.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(f.pp,i.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(f.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist48) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist48)<- "Between f.pp and i.pp"

ArchEv_dist49<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,a.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(g.pp,a.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(g.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist49) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist49)<- "Between g.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist50<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,b.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(g.pp,b.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(g.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist50) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist50)<- "Between g.pp and b.pp"

ArchEv_dist51<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,c.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(g.pp,c.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(g.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist51) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist51)<- "Between g.pp and c.pp"

ArchEv_dist52<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,d.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(g.pp,d.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(g.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist52) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist52)<- "Between g.pp and d.pp"

```

```

ArchEv_dist53<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,e.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(g.pp,e.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(g.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist53) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist53)<- "Between g.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist54<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,f.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(g.pp,f.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(g.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist54) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist54)<- "Between g.pp and f.pp"

ArchEv_dist55<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,h.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(g.pp,h.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(g.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist55) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist55)<- "Between g.pp and h.pp"

ArchEv_dist56<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(g.pp,i.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(g.pp,i.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(g.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist56) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist56)<- "Between g.pp and i.pp"

ArchEv_dist57<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,a.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h.pp,a.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist57) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist57)<- "Between h.pp and a.pp"

ArchEv_dist58<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,b.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,b.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist58) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist58)<- "Between h.pp and b.pp"

ArchEv_dist59<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,c.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,c.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist59) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist59)<- "Between h.pp and c.pp"

ArchEv_dist60<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,d.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,d.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist60) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist60)<- "Between h.pp and d.pp"

ArchEv_dist61<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,e.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,e.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist61) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist61)<- "Between h.pp and e.pp"

ArchEv_dist62<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,f.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,f.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist62) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist62)<- "Between h.pp and f.pp"

```

```
ArchEv_dist63<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,g.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,g.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist63) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist63)<- "Between h.pp and g.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist64<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(h.pp,i.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(h.pp,i.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(h.pp,i.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist64) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist64)<- "Between h.pp and i.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist65<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,a.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,a.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,a.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist65) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist65)<- "Between i.pp and a.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist66<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,b.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,b.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,b.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist66) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist66)<- "Between i.pp and b.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist67<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,c.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,c.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,c.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist67) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist67)<- "Between i.pp and c.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist68<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,d.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,d.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,d.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist68) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist68)<- "Between i.pp and d.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist69<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,e.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,e.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,e.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist69) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist69)<- "Between i.pp and e.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist70<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,f.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,f.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,f.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist70) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist70)<- "Between i.pp and f.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist71<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,g.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,g.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,g.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist71) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(ArchEv_dist71)<- "Between i.pp and g.pp"
```

```
ArchEv_dist72<-data.frame(mean(crossdist(i.pp,h.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i.pp,h.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i.pp,h.pp)))
names(ArchEv_dist72) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
```

```

row.names(ArchEv_dist72)<- "Between i.pp and h.pp"

##Archaeological Evidence (SUBCATEGORIES):

SubCat_dist1<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1)<- "Between a_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist2<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist2) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist2)<- "Between a_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist3<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist3) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist3)<- "Between a_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist4<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist4) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist4)<- "Between a_1.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5)<- "Between a_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist6<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist6) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist6)<- "Between a_1.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist7<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist7) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist7)<- "Between a_1.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist8<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist8) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist8)<- "Between a_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist9<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist9) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist9)<- "Between a_1.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist10<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist10) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist10)<- "Between a_1.pp and d_1.pp"

```

```

SubCat_dist11<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist11) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist11)<- "Between a_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist12<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist12) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist12)<- "Between a_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist13<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist13) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist13)<- "Between a_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist14<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist14) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist14)<- "Between a_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist15<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist15) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist15)<- "Between a_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist16<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist16) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist16)<- "Between a_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist17<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist17) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist17)<- "Between a_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist18<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist18) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist18)<- "Between a_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist19<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist19) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist19)<- "Between a_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist20<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist20) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist20)<- "Between a_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist21<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist21) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",

```

```

      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist21)<- "Between a_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist22<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist22) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist22)<- "Between a_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist23<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist23) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist23)<- "Between a_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist24<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist24) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist24)<- "Between a_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist25<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist25) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist25)<- "Between a_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist26<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist26) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist26)<- "Between a_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist27<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist27) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist27)<- "Between a_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist28<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist28) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist28)<- "Between a_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist29<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist29) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist29)<- "Between a_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist30<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist30) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist30)<- "Between a_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist31<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
      max(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist31) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
      "Min Euclidean Dist",
      "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist31)<- "Between a_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist32<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
      min(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_3.pp)),

```

```

        max(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_3.pp))
names(SubCat_dist32) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist32)<- "Between a_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist33<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist33) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist33)<- "Between a_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist34<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist34) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist34)<- "Between a_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist35<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist35) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist35)<- "Between a_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist36<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist36) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist36)<- "Between a_2.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist37<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist37) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist37)<- "Between a_2.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist38<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist38) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist38)<- "Between a_2.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist39<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist39) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist39)<- "Between a_2.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist40<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist40) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist40)<- "Between a_2.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist41<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist41) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist41)<- "Between a_2.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist42<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist42) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist42)<- "Between a_2.pp and b_4.pp"

```

```

SubCat_dist43<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist43) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist43)<- "Between a_2.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist44<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist44) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist44)<- "Between a_2.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist45<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist45) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist45)<- "Between a_2.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist46<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist46) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist46)<- "Between a_2.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist47<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist47) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist47)<- "Between a_2.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist48<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist48) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist48)<- "Between a_2.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist49<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist49) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist49)<- "Between a_2.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist50<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist50) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist50)<- "Between a_2.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist51<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_1.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist51) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist51)<- "Between a_2.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist52<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist52) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist52)<- "Between a_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist53<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_2.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist53) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

```

```

                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist53)<- "Between a_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist54<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist54) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist54)<- "Between a_2.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist55<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist55) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist55)<- "Between a_2.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist56<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist56) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist56)<- "Between a_2.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist57<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist57) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist57)<- "Between a_2.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist58<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist58) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist58)<- "Between a_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist59<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist59) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist59)<- "Between a_2.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist60<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist60) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist60)<- "Between a_2.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist61<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist61) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist61)<- "Between a_2.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist62<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist62) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist62)<- "Between a_2.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist63<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist63) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist63)<- "Between a_2.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist64<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_5.pp)),

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        min(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
        max(crossdist(a_2.pp,h_5.pp))
names(SubCat_dist64) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist64)<- "Between a_2.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist65<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist65) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist65)<- "Between a_2.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist66<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist66) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist66)<- "Between a_2.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist67<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist67) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist67)<- "Between a_2.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist68<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist68) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist68)<- "Between a_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist69<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist69) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist69)<- "Between a_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist70<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_2.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist70) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist70)<- "Between a_2.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist71<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist71) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist71)<- "Between a_3.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist72<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist72) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist72)<- "Between a_3.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist73<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_3.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist73) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist73)<- "Between a_3.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist74<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(a_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(a_3.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist74) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist85) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist85) <- "Between a_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist86<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist86) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist86) <- "Between a_3.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist87<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_2.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_2.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist87) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist87) <- "Between a_3.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist88<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_3.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_3.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist88) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist88) <- "Between a_3.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist89<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_1.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_1.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist89) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist89) <- "Between a_3.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist90<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_2.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_2.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist90) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist90) <- "Between a_3.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist91<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_3.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_3.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist91) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist91) <- "Between a_3.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist92<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_4.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_4.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist92) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist92) <- "Between a_3.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist93<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_5.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_5.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist93) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist93) <- "Between a_3.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist94<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_6.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_6.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist94) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist94) <- "Between a_3.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist95<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(a_3.pp, h_1.pp)),
                          min(crosssdist(a_3.pp, h_1.pp)),
                          max(crosssdist(a_3.pp, h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist95) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist95) <- "Between a_3.pp and h_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist96<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist96) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist96)<- "Between a_3.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist97<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist97) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist97)<- "Between a_3.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist98<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist98) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist98)<- "Between a_3.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist99<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                           min(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                           max(crossdist(a_3.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist99) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist99)<- "Between a_3.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist100<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist100) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist100)<- "Between a_3.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist101<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist101) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist101)<- "Between a_3.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist102<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist102) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist102)<- "Between a_3.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist103<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist103) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist103)<- "Between a_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist104<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist104) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist104)<- "Between a_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist105<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(a_3.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist105) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist105)<- "Between a_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist106<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist106) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_1.pp))
names(SubCat_dist117) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist117)<- "Between b_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist118<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist118) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist118)<- "Between b_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist119<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist119) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist119)<- "Between b_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist120<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist120) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist120)<- "Between b_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist121<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist121) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist121)<- "Between b_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist122<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist122) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist122)<- "Between b_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist123<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist123) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist123)<- "Between b_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist124<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist124) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist124)<- "Between b_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist125<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist125) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist125)<- "Between b_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist126<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist126) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist126)<- "Between b_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist127<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist127) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist127)<- "Between b_1.pp and g_4.pp"

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SubCat_dist128<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist128) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist128)<- "Between b_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist129<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist129) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist129)<- "Between b_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist130<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist130) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist130)<- "Between b_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist131<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist131) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist131)<- "Between b_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist132<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist132) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist132)<- "Between b_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist133<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist133) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist133)<- "Between b_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist134<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist134) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist134)<- "Between b_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist135<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist135) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist135)<- "Between b_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist136<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist136) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist136)<- "Between b_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist137<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist137) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist137)<- "Between b_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist138<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist138) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist138)<- "Between b_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist139<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist139) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist139)<- "Between b_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist140<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist140) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist140)<- "Between b_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist141<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist141) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist141)<- "Between b_2.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist142<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist142) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist142)<- "Between b_2.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist143<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist143) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist143)<- "Between b_2.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist144<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist144) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist144)<- "Between b_2.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist145<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist145) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist145)<- "Between b_2.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist146<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist146) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist146)<- "Between b_2.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist147<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist147) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist147)<- "Between b_2.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist148<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist148) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist148)<- "Between b_2.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist149<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,c_1.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(b_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                max(crossdist(b_2.pp,c_1.pp))
names(SubCat_dist149) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist149)<- "Between b_2.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist150<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist150) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist150)<- "Between b_2.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist151<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist151) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist151)<- "Between b_2.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist152<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist152) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist152)<- "Between b_2.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist153<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist153) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist153)<- "Between b_2.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist154<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist154) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist154)<- "Between b_2.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist155<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist155) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist155)<- "Between b_2.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist156<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist156) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist156)<- "Between b_2.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist157<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist157) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist157)<- "Between b_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist158<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist158) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist158)<- "Between b_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist159<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_2.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist159) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist170) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist170)<- "Between b_2.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist171<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist171) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist171)<- "Between b_2.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist172<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist172) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist172)<- "Between b_2.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist173<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist173) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist173)<- "Between b_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist174<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist174) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist174)<- "Between b_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist175<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_2.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist175) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist175)<- "Between b_2.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist176<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist176) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist176)<- "Between b_3.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist177<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist177) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist177)<- "Between b_3.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist178<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist178) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist178)<- "Between b_3.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist179<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist179) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist179)<- "Between b_3.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist180<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist180) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist180)<- "Between b_3.pp and b_2.pp"

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SubCat_dist181<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist181) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist181)<- "Between b_3.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist182<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist182) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist182)<- "Between b_3.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist183<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist183) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist183)<- "Between b_3.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist184<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist184) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist184)<- "Between b_3.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist185<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist185) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist185)<- "Between b_3.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist186<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist186) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist186)<- "Between b_3.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist187<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist187) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist187)<- "Between b_3.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist188<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist188) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist188)<- "Between b_3.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist189<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist189) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist189)<- "Between b_3.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist190<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist190) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist190)<- "Between b_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist191<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist191) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_3.pp))
names(SubCat_dist202) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist202)<- "Between b_3.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist203<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist203) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist203)<- "Between b_3.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist204<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist204) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist204)<- "Between b_3.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist205<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist205) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist205)<- "Between b_3.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist206<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist206) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist206)<- "Between b_3.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist207<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist207) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist207)<- "Between b_3.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist208<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist208) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist208)<- "Between b_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist209<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist209) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist209)<- "Between b_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist210<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_3.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist210) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist210)<- "Between b_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist211<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist211) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist211)<- "Between b_4.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist212<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist212) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist212)<- "Between b_4.pp and a_2.pp"

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SubCat_dist213<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist213) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist213)<- "Between b_4.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist214<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist214) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist214)<- "Between b_4.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist215<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist215) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist215)<- "Between b_4.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist216<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist216) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist216)<- "Between b_4.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist217<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist217) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist217)<- "Between b_4.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist218<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist218) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist218)<- "Between b_4.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist219<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist219) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist219)<- "Between b_4.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist220<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist220) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist220)<- "Between b_4.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist221<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist221) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist221)<- "Between b_4.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist222<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist222) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist222)<- "Between b_4.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist223<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist223) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist223)<- "Between b_4.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist224<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist224) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist224)<- "Between b_4.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist225<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist225) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist225)<- "Between b_4.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist226<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist226) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist226)<- "Between b_4.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist227<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist227) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist227)<- "Between b_4.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist228<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist228) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist228)<- "Between b_4.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist229<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist229) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist229)<- "Between b_4.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist230<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist230) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist230)<- "Between b_4.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist231<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist231) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist231)<- "Between b_4.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist232<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist232) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist232)<- "Between b_4.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist233<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist233) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist233)<- "Between b_4.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist234<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_6.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_6.pp)),
                max(crossdist(b_4.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist234) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist234)<- "Between b_4.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist235<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist235) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist235)<- "Between b_4.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist236<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist236) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist236)<- "Between b_4.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist237<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist237) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist237)<- "Between b_4.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist238<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist238) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist238)<- "Between b_4.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist239<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist239) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist239)<- "Between b_4.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist240<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist240) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist240)<- "Between b_4.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist241<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist241) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist241)<- "Between b_4.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist242<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist242) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist242)<- "Between b_4.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist243<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist243) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist243)<- "Between b_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist244<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist244) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist255) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist255)<- "Between b_5.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist256<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist256) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist256)<- "Between b_5.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist257<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist257) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist257)<- "Between b_5.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist258<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist258) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist258)<- "Between b_5.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist259<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist259) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist259)<- "Between b_5.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist260<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist260) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist260)<- "Between b_5.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist261<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist261) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist261)<- "Between b_5.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist262<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist262) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist262)<- "Between b_5.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist263<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist263) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist263)<- "Between b_5.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist264<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist264) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist264)<- "Between b_5.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist265<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist265) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist265)<- "Between b_5.pp and g_2.pp"

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SubCat_dist266<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist266) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist266)<- "Between b_5.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist267<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist267) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist267)<- "Between b_5.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist268<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist268) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist268)<- "Between b_5.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist269<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist269) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist269)<- "Between b_5.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist270<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist270) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist270)<- "Between b_5.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist271<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist271) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist271)<- "Between b_5.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist272<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist272) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist272)<- "Between b_5.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist273<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist273) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist273)<- "Between b_5.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist274<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist274) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist274)<- "Between b_5.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist275<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist275) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist275)<- "Between b_5.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist276<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(b_5.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(b_5.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(b_5.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist276) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(c_1.pp,b_4.pp))
names(SubCat_dist287) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist287)<- "Between c_1.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist288<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist288) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist288)<- "Between c_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist289<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist289) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist289)<- "Between c_1.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist290<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist290) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist290)<- "Between c_1.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist291<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist291) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist291)<- "Between c_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist292<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist292) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist292)<- "Between c_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist293<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist293) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist293)<- "Between c_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist294<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist294) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist294)<- "Between c_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist295<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist295) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist295)<- "Between c_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist296<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_1.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist296) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist296)<- "Between c_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist297<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                          min(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                          max(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist297) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                        "Min Euclidean Dist",
                        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist297)<- "Between c_1.pp and f_2.pp"

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SubCat_dist298<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist298) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist298)<- "Between c_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist299<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist299) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist299)<- "Between c_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist300<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist300) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist300)<- "Between c_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist301<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist301) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist301)<- "Between c_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist302<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist302) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist302)<- "Between c_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist303<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist303) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist303)<- "Between c_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist304<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist304) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist304)<- "Between c_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist305<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist305) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist305)<- "Between c_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist306<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist306) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist306)<- "Between c_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist307<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist307) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist307)<- "Between c_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist308<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist308) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist308)<- "Between c_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist309<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist309) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist309)<- "Between c_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist310<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist310) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist310)<- "Between c_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist311<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist311) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist311)<- "Between c_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist312<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist312) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist312)<- "Between c_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist313<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist313) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist313)<- "Between c_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist314<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist314) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist314)<- "Between c_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist315<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(c_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist315) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist315)<- "Between c_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist316<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist316) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist316)<- "Between d_1.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist317<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist317) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist317)<- "Between d_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist318<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist318) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist318)<- "Between d_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist319<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_1.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                max(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_1.pp))
names(SubCat_dist319) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist319)<- "Between d_1.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist320<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist320) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist320)<- "Between d_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist321<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist321) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist321)<- "Between d_1.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist322<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist322) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist322)<- "Between d_1.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist323<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist323) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist323)<- "Between d_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist324<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist324) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist324)<- "Between d_1.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist325<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist325) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist325)<- "Between d_1.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist326<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist326) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist326)<- "Between d_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist327<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist327) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist327)<- "Between d_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist328<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist328) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist328)<- "Between d_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist329<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist329) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist340) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist340) <- "Between d_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist341 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist341) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist341) <- "Between d_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist342 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist342) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist342) <- "Between d_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist343 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist343) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist343) <- "Between d_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist344 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist344) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist344) <- "Between d_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist345 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist345) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist345) <- "Between d_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist346 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist346) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist346) <- "Between d_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist347 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist347) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist347) <- "Between d_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist348 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist348) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist348) <- "Between d_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist349 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist349) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist349) <- "Between d_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist350 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_1.pp, i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist350) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist350) <- "Between d_1.pp and i_5.pp"

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SubCat_dist351<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist351) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist351)<- "Between d_2.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist352<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist352) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist352)<- "Between d_2.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist353<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist353) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist353)<- "Between d_2.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist354<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist354) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist354)<- "Between d_2.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist355<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist355) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist355)<- "Between d_2.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist356<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist356) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist356)<- "Between d_2.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist357<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist357) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist357)<- "Between d_2.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist358<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist358) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist358)<- "Between d_2.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist359<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist359) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist359)<- "Between d_2.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist360<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist360) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist360)<- "Between d_2.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist361<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist361) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_4.pp))
names(SubCat_dist372) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist372)<- "Between d_2.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist373<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist373) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist373)<- "Between d_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist374<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist374) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist374)<- "Between d_2.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist375<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist375) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist375)<- "Between d_2.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist376<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist376) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist376)<- "Between d_2.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist377<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist377) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist377)<- "Between d_2.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist378<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist378) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist378)<- "Between d_2.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist379<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist379) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist379)<- "Between d_2.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist380<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist380) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist380)<- "Between d_2.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist381<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist381) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist381)<- "Between d_2.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist382<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist382) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist382)<- "Between d_2.pp and i_3.pp"

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SubCat_dist383<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist383) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist383)<- "Between d_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist384<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist384) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist384)<- "Between d_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist385<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(d_2.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist385) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist385)<- "Between d_2.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist386<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist386) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist386)<- "Between e_1.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist387<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist387) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist387)<- "Between e_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist388<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist388) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist388)<- "Between e_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist389<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist389) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist389)<- "Between e_1.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist390<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist390) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist390)<- "Between e_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist391<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist391) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist391)<- "Between e_1.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist392<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist392) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist392)<- "Between e_1.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist393<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist393) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist393)<- "Between e_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist394<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist394) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist394)<- "Between e_1.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist395<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist395) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist395)<- "Between e_1.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist396<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist396) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist396)<- "Between e_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist397<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist397) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist397)<- "Between e_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist398<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist398) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist398)<- "Between e_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist399<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist399) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist399)<- "Between e_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist400<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist400) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist400)<- "Between e_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist401<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist401) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist401)<- "Between e_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist402<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist402) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist402)<- "Between e_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist403<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_1.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist403) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist403)<- "Between e_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist404<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_1.pp,g_1.pp)),

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                min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist404) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist404)<- "Between e_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist405<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist405) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist405)<- "Between e_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist406<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist406) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist406)<- "Between e_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist407<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist407) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist407)<- "Between e_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist408<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist408) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist408)<- "Between e_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist409<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist409) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist409)<- "Between e_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist410<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist410) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist410)<- "Between e_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist411<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist411) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist411)<- "Between e_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist412<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist412) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist412)<- "Between e_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist413<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist413) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist413)<- "Between e_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist414<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(e_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist414) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist425) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist425) <- "Between e_2.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist426 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist426) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist426) <- "Between e_2.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist427 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist427) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist427) <- "Between e_2.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist428 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist428) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist428) <- "Between e_2.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist429 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist429) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist429) <- "Between e_2.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist430 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist430) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist430) <- "Between e_2.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist431 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist431) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist431) <- "Between e_2.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist432 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist432) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist432) <- "Between e_2.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist433 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist433) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist433) <- "Between e_2.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist434 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist434) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist434) <- "Between e_2.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist435 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist435) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist435) <- "Between e_2.pp and e_4.pp"

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SubCat_dist436<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist436) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist436)<- "Between e_2.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist437<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist437) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist437)<- "Between e_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist438<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist438) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist438)<- "Between e_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist439<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist439) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist439)<- "Between e_2.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist440<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist440) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist440)<- "Between e_2.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist441<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist441) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist441)<- "Between e_2.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist442<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist442) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist442)<- "Between e_2.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist443<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist443) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist443)<- "Between e_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist444<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist444) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist444)<- "Between e_2.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist445<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist445) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist445)<- "Between e_2.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist446<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_2.pp, h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_2.pp, h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_2.pp, h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist446) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(e_3.pp,a_2.pp))
names(SubCat_dist457) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist457)<- "Between e_3.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist458<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist458) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist458)<- "Between e_3.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist459<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist459) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist459)<- "Between e_3.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist460<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist460) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist460)<- "Between e_3.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist461<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist461) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist461)<- "Between e_3.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist462<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist462) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist462)<- "Between e_3.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist463<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist463) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist463)<- "Between e_3.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist464<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist464) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist464)<- "Between e_3.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist465<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist465) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist465)<- "Between e_3.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist466<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist466) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist466)<- "Between e_3.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist467<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist467) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist467)<- "Between e_3.pp and e_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist468<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist468) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist468)<- "Between e_3.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist469<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist469) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist469)<- "Between e_3.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist470<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist470) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist470)<- "Between e_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist471<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist471) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist471)<- "Between e_3.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist472<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist472) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist472)<- "Between e_3.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist473<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist473) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist473)<- "Between e_3.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist474<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist474) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist474)<- "Between e_3.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist475<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist475) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist475)<- "Between e_3.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist476<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist476) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist476)<- "Between e_3.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist477<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist477) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist477)<- "Between e_3.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist478<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist478) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist478)<- "Between e_3.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist479<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist479) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist479)<- "Between e_3.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist480<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist480) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist480)<- "Between e_3.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist481<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist481) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist481)<- "Between e_3.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist482<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist482) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist482)<- "Between e_3.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist483<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist483) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist483)<- "Between e_3.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist484<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist484) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist484)<- "Between e_3.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist485<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist485) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist485)<- "Between e_3.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist486<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist486) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist486)<- "Between e_3.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist487<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist487) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist487)<- "Between e_3.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist488<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist488) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist488)<- "Between e_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist489<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_3.pp,i_4.pp)),

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                min(crosssdist(e_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                max(crosssdist(e_3.pp,i_4.pp))
names(SubCat_dist489) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist489)<- "Between e_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist490<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_3.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist490) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist490)<- "Between e_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist491<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist491) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist491)<- "Between e_4.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist492<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist492) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist492)<- "Between e_4.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist493<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist493) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist493)<- "Between e_4.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist494<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist494) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist494)<- "Between e_4.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist495<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist495) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist495)<- "Between e_4.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist496<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist496) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist496)<- "Between e_4.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist497<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist497) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist497)<- "Between e_4.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist498<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist498) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist498)<- "Between e_4.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist499<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(e_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crosssdist(e_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crosssdist(e_4.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist499) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist510) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist510)<- "Between e_4.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist511<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist511) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist511)<- "Between e_4.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist512<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist512) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist512)<- "Between e_4.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist513<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist513) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist513)<- "Between e_4.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist514<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist514) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist514)<- "Between e_4.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist515<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist515) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist515)<- "Between e_4.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist516<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist516) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist516)<- "Between e_4.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist517<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist517) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist517)<- "Between e_4.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist518<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist518) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist518)<- "Between e_4.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist519<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist519) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist519)<- "Between e_4.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist520<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist520) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist520)<- "Between e_4.pp and i_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist521<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist521) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist521)<- "Between e_4.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist522<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist522) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist522)<- "Between e_4.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist523<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist523) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist523)<- "Between e_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist524<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist524) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist524)<- "Between e_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist525<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(e_4.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist525) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist525)<- "Between e_4.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist526<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist526) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist526)<- "Between f_1.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist527<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist527) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist527)<- "Between f_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist528<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist528) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist528)<- "Between f_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist529<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist529) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist529)<- "Between f_1.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist530<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist530) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist530)<- "Between f_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist531<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist531) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(f_1.pp,f_2.pp))
names(SubCat_dist542) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist542)<- "Between f_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist543<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist543) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist543)<- "Between f_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist544<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist544) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist544)<- "Between f_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist545<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist545) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist545)<- "Between f_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist546<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist546) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist546)<- "Between f_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist547<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist547) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist547)<- "Between f_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist548<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist548) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist548)<- "Between f_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist549<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist549) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist549)<- "Between f_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist550<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist550) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist550)<- "Between f_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist551<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist551) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist551)<- "Between f_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist552<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist552) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist552)<- "Between f_1.pp and h_3.pp"

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SubCat_dist553<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist553) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist553)<- "Between f_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist554<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist554) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist554)<- "Between f_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist555<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist555) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist555)<- "Between f_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist556<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist556) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist556)<- "Between f_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist557<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist557) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist557)<- "Between f_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist558<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist558) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist558)<- "Between f_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist559<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist559) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist559)<- "Between f_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist560<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist560) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist560)<- "Between f_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist561<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist561) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist561)<- "Between f_2.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist562<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist562) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist562)<- "Between f_2.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist563<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_2.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist563) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist563)<- "Between f_2.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist564<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist564) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist564)<- "Between f_2.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist565<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist565) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist565)<- "Between f_2.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist566<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist566) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist566)<- "Between f_2.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist567<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist567) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist567)<- "Between f_2.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist568<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist568) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist568)<- "Between f_2.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist569<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist569) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist569)<- "Between f_2.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist570<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist570) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist570)<- "Between f_2.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist571<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist571) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist571)<- "Between f_2.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist572<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist572) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist572)<- "Between f_2.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist573<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist573) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist573)<- "Between f_2.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist574<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_3.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                max(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist574) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist574)<- "Between f_2.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist575<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist575) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist575)<- "Between f_2.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist576<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist576) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist576)<- "Between f_2.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist577<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist577) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist577)<- "Between f_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist578<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist578) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist578)<- "Between f_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist579<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist579) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist579)<- "Between f_2.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist580<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist580) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist580)<- "Between f_2.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist581<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist581) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist581)<- "Between f_2.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist582<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist582) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist582)<- "Between f_2.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist583<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist583) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist583)<- "Between f_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist584<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(f_2.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist584) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist595) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist595) <- "Between f_2.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist5596 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5596) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5596) <- "Between f_3.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5597 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5597) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5597) <- "Between f_3.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist5598 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5598) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5598) <- "Between f_3.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist5599 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5599) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5599) <- "Between f_3.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5600 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5600) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5600) <- "Between f_3.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist5601 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5601) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5601) <- "Between f_3.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist5602 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5602) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5602) <- "Between f_3.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist5603 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5603) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5603) <- "Between f_3.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist5604 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5604) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5604) <- "Between f_3.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5605 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp, d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp, d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5605) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5605) <- "Between f_3.pp and d_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist5606<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5606) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5606)<- "Between f_3.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist5607<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5607) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5607)<- "Between f_3.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5608<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5608) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5608)<- "Between f_3.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist5609<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5609) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5609)<- "Between f_3.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist5610<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5610) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5610)<- "Between f_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist5611<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5611) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5611)<- "Between f_3.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5612<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5612) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5612)<- "Between f_3.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist5613<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5613) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5613)<- "Between f_3.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist5614<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5614) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5614)<- "Between f_3.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist5615<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5615) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5615)<- "Between f_3.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist5616<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(f_3.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5616) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5627) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5627)<- "Between f_3.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist5628<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
        min(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
        max(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5628) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5628)<- "Between f_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist5629<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
        min(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
        max(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5629) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5629)<- "Between f_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist5630<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
        min(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
        max(crossdist(f_3.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist5630) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist5630)<- "Between f_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist596<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist596) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist596)<- "Between g_1.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist597<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist597) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist597)<- "Between g_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist598<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist598) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist598)<- "Between g_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist599<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist599) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist599)<- "Between g_1.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist600<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist600) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist600)<- "Between g_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist601<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist601) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist601)<- "Between g_1.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist602<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
        min(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
        max(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist602) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
        "Min Euclidean Dist",
        "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist602)<- "Between g_1.pp and b_4.pp"

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SubCat_dist603<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist603) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist603)<- "Between g_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist604<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist604) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist604)<- "Between g_1.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist605<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist605) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist605)<- "Between g_1.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist606<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist606) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist606)<- "Between g_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist607<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist607) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist607)<- "Between g_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist608<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist608) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist608)<- "Between g_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist609<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist609) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist609)<- "Between g_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist610<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist610) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist610)<- "Between g_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist611<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist611) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist611)<- "Between g_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist612<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist612) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist612)<- "Between g_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist613<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist613) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

```

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist613)<- "Between g_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist614<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist614) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist614)<- "Between g_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist615<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist615) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist615)<- "Between g_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist616<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist616) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist616)<- "Between g_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist617<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist617) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist617)<- "Between g_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist618<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist618) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist618)<- "Between g_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist619<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist619) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist619)<- "Between g_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist620<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist620) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist620)<- "Between g_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist621<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist621) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist621)<- "Between g_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist622<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist622) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist622)<- "Between g_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist623<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist623) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist623)<- "Between g_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist624<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_5.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                max(crossdist(g_1.pp,h_5.pp))
names(SubCat_dist624) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist624)<- "Between g_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist625<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist625) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist625)<- "Between g_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist626<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist626) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist626)<- "Between g_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist627<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist627) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist627)<- "Between g_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist628<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist628) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist628)<- "Between g_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist629<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist629) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist629)<- "Between g_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist630<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist630) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist630)<- "Between g_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist631<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist631) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist631)<- "Between g_2.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist632<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist632) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist632)<- "Between g_2.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist633<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist633) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist633)<- "Between g_2.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist634<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist634) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(g_2.pp,e_4.pp))
names(SubCat_dist645) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist645)<- "Between g_2.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist646<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist646) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist646)<- "Between g_2.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist647<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist647) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist647)<- "Between g_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist648<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist648) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist648)<- "Between g_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist649<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist649) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist649)<- "Between g_2.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist650<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist650) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist650)<- "Between g_2.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist651<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist651) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist651)<- "Between g_2.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist652<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist652) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist652)<- "Between g_2.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist653<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist653) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist653)<- "Between g_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist654<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist654) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist654)<- "Between g_2.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist655<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist655) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist655)<- "Between g_2.pp and h_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist656<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist656) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist656)<- "Between g_2.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist657<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist657) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist657)<- "Between g_2.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist658<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist658) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist658)<- "Between g_2.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist659<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist659) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist659)<- "Between g_2.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist660<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist660) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist660)<- "Between g_2.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist661<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist661) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist661)<- "Between g_2.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist662<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist662) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist662)<- "Between g_2.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist663<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist663) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist663)<- "Between g_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist664<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist664) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist664)<- "Between g_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist665<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_2.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist665) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist665)<- "Between g_2.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist666<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist666) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

```

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist666)<- "Between g_3.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist667<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist667) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist667)<- "Between g_3.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist668<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist668) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist668)<- "Between g_3.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist669<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist669) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist669)<- "Between g_3.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist670<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist670) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist670)<- "Between g_3.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist671<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist671) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist671)<- "Between g_3.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist672<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist672) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist672)<- "Between g_3.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist673<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist673) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist673)<- "Between g_3.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist674<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist674) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist674)<- "Between g_3.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist675<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist675) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist675)<- "Between g_3.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist676<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_3.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist676) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist676)<- "Between g_3.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist677<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp,e_1.pp)),

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                min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist677) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist677)<- "Between g_3.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist678<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist678) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist678)<- "Between g_3.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist679<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist679) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist679)<- "Between g_3.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist680<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist680) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist680)<- "Between g_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist681<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist681) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist681)<- "Between g_3.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist682<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist682) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist682)<- "Between g_3.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist683<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist683) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist683)<- "Between g_3.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist684<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist684) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist684)<- "Between g_3.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist685<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist685) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist685)<- "Between g_3.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist686<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist686) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist686)<- "Between g_3.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist687<- data.frame(mean(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crosssdist(g_3.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist687) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist698) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist698) <- "Between g_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist699 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp, i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_3.pp, i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_3.pp, i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist699) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist699) <- "Between g_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist700 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_3.pp, i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_3.pp, i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_3.pp, i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist700) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist700) <- "Between g_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist701 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist701) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist701) <- "Between g_4.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist702 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist702) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist702) <- "Between g_4.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist703 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist703) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist703) <- "Between g_4.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist704 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist704) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist704) <- "Between g_4.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist705 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist705) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist705) <- "Between g_4.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist706 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist706) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist706) <- "Between g_4.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist707 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist707) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist707) <- "Between g_4.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist708 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp, b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist708) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist708) <- "Between g_4.pp and b_5.pp"

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SubCat_dist709<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist709) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist709)<- "Between g_4.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist710<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist710) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist710)<- "Between g_4.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist711<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist711) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist711)<- "Between g_4.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist712<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist712) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist712)<- "Between g_4.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist713<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist713) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist713)<- "Between g_4.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist714<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist714) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist714)<- "Between g_4.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist715<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist715) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist715)<- "Between g_4.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist716<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist716) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist716)<- "Between g_4.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist717<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist717) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist717)<- "Between g_4.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist718<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist718) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist718)<- "Between g_4.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist719<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist719) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist719)<- "Between g_4.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist720<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist720) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist720)<- "Between g_4.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist721<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist721) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist721)<- "Between g_4.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist722<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist722) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist722)<- "Between g_4.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist723<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist723) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist723)<- "Between g_4.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist724<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist724) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist724)<- "Between g_4.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist725<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist725) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist725)<- "Between g_4.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist726<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist726) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist726)<- "Between g_4.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist727<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist727) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist727)<- "Between g_4.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist728<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist728) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist728)<- "Between g_4.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist729<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist729) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist729)<- "Between g_4.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist730<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_1.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                max(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_1.pp))
names(SubCat_dist730) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist730)<- "Between g_4.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist731<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist731) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist731)<- "Between g_4.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist732<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist732) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist732)<- "Between g_4.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist733<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist733) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist733)<- "Between g_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist734<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist734) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist734)<- "Between g_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist735<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_4.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist735) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist735)<- "Between g_4.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist736<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist736) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist736)<- "Between g_5.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist737<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist737) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist737)<- "Between g_5.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist738<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist738) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist738)<- "Between g_5.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist739<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist739) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist739)<- "Between g_5.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist740<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist740) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",

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```

        max(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_1.pp))
names(SubCat_dist751) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist751)<- "Between g_5.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist752<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist752) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist752)<- "Between g_5.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist753<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist753) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist753)<- "Between g_5.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist754<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist754) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist754)<- "Between g_5.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist755<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist755) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist755)<- "Between g_5.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist756<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist756) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist756)<- "Between g_5.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist757<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist757) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist757)<- "Between g_5.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist758<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist758) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist758)<- "Between g_5.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist759<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist759) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist759)<- "Between g_5.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist760<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,h_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist760) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist760)<- "Between g_5.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist761<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_5.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_5.pp,h_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_5.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist761) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist761)<- "Between g_5.pp and h_2.pp"

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names(SubCat_dist772) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist772)<- "Between g_6.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist773<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist773) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist773)<- "Between g_6.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist774<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist774) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist774)<- "Between g_6.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist775<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist775) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist775)<- "Between g_6.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist776<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist776) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist776)<- "Between g_6.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist777<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist777) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist777)<- "Between g_6.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist778<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist778) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist778)<- "Between g_6.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist779<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist779) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist779)<- "Between g_6.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist780<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist780) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist780)<- "Between g_6.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist781<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,d_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist781) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist781)<- "Between g_6.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist782<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist782) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist782)<- "Between g_6.pp and e_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist783<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist783) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist783)<- "Between g_6.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist784<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist784) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist784)<- "Between g_6.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist785<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist785) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist785)<- "Between g_6.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist786<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist786) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist786)<- "Between g_6.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist787<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist787) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist787)<- "Between g_6.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist788<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist788) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist788)<- "Between g_6.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist789<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist789) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist789)<- "Between g_6.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist790<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist790) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist790)<- "Between g_6.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist791<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist791) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist791)<- "Between g_6.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist792<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist792) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist792)<- "Between g_6.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist793<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(g_6.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist793) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

```



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        max(crossdist(g_6.pp,i_4.pp))
names(SubCat_dist804) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist804)<- "Between g_6.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist805<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(g_6.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(g_6.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(g_6.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist805) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist805)<- "Between g_6.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist806<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist806) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist806)<- "Between h_1.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist807<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist807) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist807)<- "Between h_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist808<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist808) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist808)<- "Between h_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist809<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist809) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist809)<- "Between h_1.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist810<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist810) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist810)<- "Between h_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist811<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist811) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist811)<- "Between h_1.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist812<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist812) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist812)<- "Between h_1.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist813<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist813) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist813)<- "Between h_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist814<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist814) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist814)<- "Between h_1.pp and c_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist815<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist815) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist815)<- "Between h_1.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist816<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist816) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist816)<- "Between h_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist817<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist817) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist817)<- "Between h_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist818<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist818) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist818)<- "Between h_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist819<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist819) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist819)<- "Between h_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist820<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist820) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist820)<- "Between h_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist821<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist821) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist821)<- "Between h_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist822<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist822) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist822)<- "Between h_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist823<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist823) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist823)<- "Between h_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist824<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp, g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist824) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist824)<- "Between h_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist825<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp, g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist825) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist825)<- "Between h_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist826<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist826) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist826)<- "Between h_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist827<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist827) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist827)<- "Between h_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist828<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist828) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist828)<- "Between h_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist829<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist829) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist829)<- "Between h_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist830<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist830) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist830)<- "Between h_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist831<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist831) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist831)<- "Between h_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist832<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist832) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist832)<- "Between h_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist833<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist833) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist833)<- "Between h_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist834<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist834) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist834)<- "Between h_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist835<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist835) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist835)<- "Between h_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist836<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_2.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                max(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist836) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist836)<- "Between h_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist837<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist837) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist837)<- "Between h_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist838<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist838) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist838)<- "Between h_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist839<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist839) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist839)<- "Between h_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist840<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist840) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist840)<- "Between h_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist841<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist841) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist841)<- "Between h_2.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist842<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist842) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist842)<- "Between h_2.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist843<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_2.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist843) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist843)<- "Between h_2.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist844<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist844) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist844)<- "Between h_2.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist845<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist845) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist845)<- "Between h_2.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist846<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_2.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist846) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist857) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist857) <- "Between h_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist858 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist858) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist858) <- "Between h_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist859 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist859) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist859) <- "Between h_2.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist860 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist860) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist860) <- "Between h_2.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist861 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist861) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist861) <- "Between h_2.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist862 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist862) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist862) <- "Between h_2.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist863 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist863) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist863) <- "Between h_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist864 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist864) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist864) <- "Between h_2.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist865 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist865) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist865) <- "Between h_2.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist866 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist866) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist866) <- "Between h_2.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist867 <- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp, h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist867) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist867) <- "Between h_2.pp and h_3.pp"

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SubCat_dist868<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist868) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist868)<- "Between h_2.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist869<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist869) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist869)<- "Between h_2.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist870<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist870) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist870)<- "Between h_2.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist871<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist871) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist871)<- "Between h_2.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist872<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist872) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist872)<- "Between h_2.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist873<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist873) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist873)<- "Between h_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist874<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist874) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist874)<- "Between h_2.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist875<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_2.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist875) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist875)<- "Between h_2.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist876<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist876) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist876)<- "Between h_3.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist877<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist877) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist877)<- "Between h_3.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist878<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist878) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(h_3.pp,e_3.pp))
names(SubCat_dist889) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist889)<- "Between h_3.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist890<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist890) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist890)<- "Between h_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist891<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist891) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist891)<- "Between h_3.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist892<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist892) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist892)<- "Between h_3.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist893<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist893) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist893)<- "Between h_3.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist894<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist894) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist894)<- "Between h_3.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist895<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist895) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist895)<- "Between h_3.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist896<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist896) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist896)<- "Between h_3.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist897<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist897) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist897)<- "Between h_3.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist898<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist898) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist898)<- "Between h_3.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist899<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_6.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_3.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist899) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist899)<- "Between h_3.pp and g_6.pp"

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SubCat_dist900<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist900) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist900)<- "Between h_3.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist901<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist901) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist901)<- "Between h_3.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist902<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist902) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist902)<- "Between h_3.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist903<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist903) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist903)<- "Between h_3.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist904<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist904) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist904)<- "Between h_3.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist905<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist905) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist905)<- "Between h_3.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist906<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist906) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist906)<- "Between h_3.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist907<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist907) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist907)<- "Between h_3.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist908<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist908) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist908)<- "Between h_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist909<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist909) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist909)<- "Between h_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist910<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_3.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist910) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist910)<- "Between h_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist911<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist911) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist911)<- "Between h_4.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist912<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist912) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist912)<- "Between h_4.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist913<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist913) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist913)<- "Between h_4.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist914<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist914) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist914)<- "Between h_4.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist915<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist915) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist915)<- "Between h_4.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist916<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist916) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist916)<- "Between h_4.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist917<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist917) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist917)<- "Between h_4.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist918<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist918) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist918)<- "Between h_4.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist919<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist919) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist919)<- "Between h_4.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist920<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_4.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist920) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist920)<- "Between h_4.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist921<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,d_2.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(h_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                max(crossdist(h_4.pp,d_2.pp))
names(SubCat_dist921) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist921)<- "Between h_4.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist922<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist922) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist922)<- "Between h_4.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist923<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist923) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist923)<- "Between h_4.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist924<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist924) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist924)<- "Between h_4.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist925<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist925) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist925)<- "Between h_4.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist926<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist926) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist926)<- "Between h_4.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist927<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist927) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist927)<- "Between h_4.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist928<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist928) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist928)<- "Between h_4.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist929<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist929) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist929)<- "Between h_4.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist930<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist930) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist930)<- "Between h_4.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist931<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp, g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist931) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist942) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist942)<- "Between h_4.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist943<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist943) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist943)<- "Between h_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist944<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist944) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist944)<- "Between h_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist945<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_4.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist945) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist945)<- "Between h_4.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist946<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist946) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist946)<- "Between h_5.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist947<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist947) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist947)<- "Between h_5.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist948<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist948) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist948)<- "Between h_5.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist949<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist949) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist949)<- "Between h_5.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist950<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist950) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist950)<- "Between h_5.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist951<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist951) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist951)<- "Between h_5.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist952<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist952) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist952)<- "Between h_5.pp and b_4.pp"

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SubCat_dist953<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist953) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist953)<- "Between h_5.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist954<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist954) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist954)<- "Between h_5.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist955<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist955) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist955)<- "Between h_5.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist956<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist956) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist956)<- "Between h_5.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist957<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist957) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist957)<- "Between h_5.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist958<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist958) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist958)<- "Between h_5.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist959<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist959) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist959)<- "Between h_5.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist960<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist960) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist960)<- "Between h_5.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist961<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist961) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist961)<- "Between h_5.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist962<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist962) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist962)<- "Between h_5.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist963<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(h_5.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist963) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(h_5.pp,h_5.pp))
names(SubCat_dist974) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist974)<- "Between h_5.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist975<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist975) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist975)<- "Between h_5.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist976<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist976) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist976)<- "Between h_5.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist977<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist977) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist977)<- "Between h_5.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist978<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist978) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist978)<- "Between h_5.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist979<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_4.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist979) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist979)<- "Between h_5.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist980<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_5.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(h_5.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist980) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist980)<- "Between h_5.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist981<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist981) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist981)<- "Between i_1.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist982<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist982) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist982)<- "Between i_1.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist983<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist983) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist983)<- "Between i_1.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist984<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist984) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist984)<- "Between i_1.pp and b_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist985<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist985) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist985)<- "Between i_1.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist986<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist986) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist986)<- "Between i_1.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist987<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist987) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist987)<- "Between i_1.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist988<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist988) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist988)<- "Between i_1.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist989<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist989) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist989)<- "Between i_1.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist990<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist990) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist990)<- "Between i_1.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist991<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist991) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist991)<- "Between i_1.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist992<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist992) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist992)<- "Between i_1.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist993<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist993) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist993)<- "Between i_1.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist994<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist994) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist994)<- "Between i_1.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist995<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist995) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

```

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                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist995)<- "Between i_1.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist996<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist996) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist996)<- "Between i_1.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist997<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_2.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_2.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist997) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist997)<- "Between i_1.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist998<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_3.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_3.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp, f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist998) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist998)<- "Between i_1.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist999<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_1.pp)),
                            min(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_1.pp)),
                            max(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist999) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist999)<- "Between i_1.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1000<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1000) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1000)<- "Between i_1.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1001<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1001) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1001)<- "Between i_1.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1002<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1002) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1002)<- "Between i_1.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1003<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1003) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1003)<- "Between i_1.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1004<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp, g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1004) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1004)<- "Between i_1.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist1005<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp, h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp, h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1005) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1005)<- "Between i_1.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1006<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp, h_2.pp)),

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                min(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_2.pp)),
                max(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1006) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1006)<- "Between i_1.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1007<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1007) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1007)<- "Between i_1.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1008<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1008) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1008)<- "Between i_1.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1009<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1009) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1009)<- "Between i_1.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1010<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1010) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1010)<- "Between i_1.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1011<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1011) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1011)<- "Between i_1.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1012<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1012) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1012)<- "Between i_1.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1013<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1013) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1013)<- "Between i_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1014<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1014) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1014)<- "Between i_1.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1015<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_1.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1015) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1015)<- "Between i_1.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1016<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1016) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")

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names(SubCat_dist1027) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1027)<- "Between i_2.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1028<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_2.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1028) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1028)<- "Between i_2.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1029<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_3.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1029) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1029)<- "Between i_2.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1030<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_4.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1030) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1030)<- "Between i_2.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1031<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp, f_1.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_1.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1031) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1031)<- "Between i_2.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1032<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_2.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1032) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1032)<- "Between i_2.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1033<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_3.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1033) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1033)<- "Between i_2.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1034<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_1.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1034) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1034)<- "Between i_2.pp and g_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1035<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_2.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1035) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1035)<- "Between i_2.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1036<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_3.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1036) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1036)<- "Between i_2.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1037<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                              min(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_4.pp)),
                              max(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1037) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1037)<- "Between i_2.pp and g_4.pp"

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SubCat_dist1038<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1038) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1038)<- "Between i_2.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1039<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1039) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1039)<- "Between i_2.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist1040<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1040) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1040)<- "Between i_2.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1041<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1041) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1041)<- "Between i_2.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1042<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1042) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1042)<- "Between i_2.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1043<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1043) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1043)<- "Between i_2.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1044<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1044) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1044)<- "Between i_2.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1045<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1045) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1045)<- "Between i_2.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1046<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1046) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1046)<- "Between i_2.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1047<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1047) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1047)<- "Between i_2.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1048<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_2.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1048) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(i_3.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1059) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1059)<- "Between i_3.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1060<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1060) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1060)<- "Between i_3.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1061<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1061) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1061)<- "Between i_3.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1062<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1062) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1062)<- "Between i_3.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1063<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1063) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1063)<- "Between i_3.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1064<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1064) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1064)<- "Between i_3.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1065<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1065) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1065)<- "Between i_3.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1066<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp, f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1066) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1066)<- "Between i_3.pp and f_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1067<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1067) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1067)<- "Between i_3.pp and f_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1068<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,f_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1068) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1068)<- "Between i_3.pp and f_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1069<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1069) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1069)<- "Between i_3.pp and g_1.pp"

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SubCat_dist1070<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1070) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1070)<- "Between i_3.pp and g_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1071<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1071) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1071)<- "Between i_3.pp and g_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1072<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1072) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1072)<- "Between i_3.pp and g_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1073<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1073) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1073)<- "Between i_3.pp and g_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1074<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_6.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1074) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1074)<- "Between i_3.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist1075<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1075) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1075)<- "Between i_3.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1076<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1076) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1076)<- "Between i_3.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1077<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1077) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1077)<- "Between i_3.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1078<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1078) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1078)<- "Between i_3.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1079<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1079) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1079)<- "Between i_3.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1080<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1080) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",

```

```

                "Min Euclidean Dist",
                "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1080)<- "Between i_3.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1081<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1081) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1081)<- "Between i_3.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1082<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1082) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1082)<- "Between i_3.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1083<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1083) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1083)<- "Between i_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1084<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1084) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1084)<- "Between i_3.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1085<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_3.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1085) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1085)<- "Between i_3.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1086<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1086) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1086)<- "Between i_4.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1087<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1087) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1087)<- "Between i_4.pp and a_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1088<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1088) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1088)<- "Between i_4.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1089<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1089) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1089)<- "Between i_4.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1090<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1090) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1090)<- "Between i_4.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1091<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_3.pp)),

```

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                min(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_3.pp)),
                max(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_3.pp))
names(SubCat_dist1091) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1091)<- "Between i_4.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1092<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1092) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1092)<- "Between i_4.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1093<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1093) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1093)<- "Between i_4.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1094<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1094) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1094)<- "Between i_4.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1095<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1095) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1095)<- "Between i_4.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1096<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1096) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1096)<- "Between i_4.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1097<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1097) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1097)<- "Between i_4.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1098<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1098) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1098)<- "Between i_4.pp and e_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1099<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1099) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1099)<- "Between i_4.pp and e_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1100<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,e_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1100) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1100)<- "Between i_4.pp and e_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1101<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,f_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,f_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1101) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")

```



```

names(SubCat_dist1112) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1112)<- "Between i_4.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1113<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1113) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1113)<- "Between i_4.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1114<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1114) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1114)<- "Between i_4.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1115<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1115) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1115)<- "Between i_4.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1116<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1116) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1116)<- "Between i_4.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1117<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1117) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1117)<- "Between i_4.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1118<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1118) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1118)<- "Between i_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1119<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1119) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1119)<- "Between i_4.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1120<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_4.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1120) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1120)<- "Between i_4.pp and i_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1121<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1121) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1121)<- "Between i_5.pp and a_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1122<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1122) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1122)<- "Between i_5.pp and a_2.pp"

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SubCat_dist1123<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,a_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1123) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1123)<- "Between i_5.pp and a_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1124<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1124) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1124)<- "Between i_5.pp and b_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1125<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1125) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1125)<- "Between i_5.pp and b_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1126<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1126) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1126)<- "Between i_5.pp and b_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1127<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1127) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1127)<- "Between i_5.pp and b_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1128<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,b_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1128) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1128)<- "Between i_5.pp and b_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1129<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,c_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,c_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1129) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1129)<- "Between i_5.pp and c_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1130<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,d_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,d_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1130) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1130)<- "Between i_5.pp and d_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1131<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,d_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,d_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1131) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1131)<- "Between i_5.pp and d_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1132<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,e_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,e_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1132) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",
                            "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1132)<- "Between i_5.pp and e_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1133<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,e_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,e_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1133) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                            "Min Euclidean Dist",

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        max(crossdist(i_5.pp,g_6.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1144) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1144)<- "Between i_5.pp and g_6.pp"

SubCat_dist1145<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1145) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1145)<- "Between i_5.pp and h_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1146<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1146) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1146)<- "Between i_5.pp and h_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1147<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1147) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1147)<- "Between i_5.pp and h_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1148<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1148) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1148)<- "Between i_5.pp and h_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1149<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,h_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1149) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1149)<- "Between i_5.pp and h_5.pp"

SubCat_dist1150<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_1.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_1.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1150) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1150)<- "Between i_5.pp and i_1.pp"

SubCat_dist1151<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_2.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_2.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1151) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1151)<- "Between i_5.pp and i_2.pp"

SubCat_dist1152<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_3.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_3.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1152) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1152)<- "Between i_5.pp and i_3.pp"

SubCat_dist1153<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_4.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_4.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1153) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1153)<- "Between i_5.pp and i_4.pp"

SubCat_dist1154<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1154) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                          "Min Euclidean Dist",
                          "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1154)<- "Between i_5.pp and i_5.pp"

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```

SubCat_dist1155<- data.frame(mean(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             min(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_5.pp)),
                             max(crossdist(i_5.pp,i_5.pp)))
names(SubCat_dist1155) <- c("Mean Euclidean Dist",
                           "Min Euclidean Dist",
                           "Max Euclidean Dist")
row.names(SubCat_dist1155)<- "Between i_5.pp and i_5.pp"

```

```
# writing table for distance values of all arch. evidence and subcats:
```

```

ArchEv_dist<- rbind(ArchEv_dist1, ArchEv_dist2,
                   ArchEv_dist3, ArchEv_dist4,
                   ArchEv_dist5, ArchEv_dist6,
                   ArchEv_dist7, ArchEv_dist8,
                   ArchEv_dist9, ArchEv_dist10,
                   ArchEv_dist11, ArchEv_dist12,
                   ArchEv_dist13, ArchEv_dist14,
                   ArchEv_dist15, ArchEv_dist16,
                   ArchEv_dist17, ArchEv_dist18,
                   ArchEv_dist19, ArchEv_dist20,
                   ArchEv_dist22, ArchEv_dist23,
                   ArchEv_dist24, ArchEv_dist25,
                   ArchEv_dist26, ArchEv_dist27,
                   ArchEv_dist28, ArchEv_dist29,
                   ArchEv_dist30, ArchEv_dist31,
                   ArchEv_dist32, ArchEv_dist33,
                   ArchEv_dist34, ArchEv_dist35,
                   ArchEv_dist36, ArchEv_dist37,
                   ArchEv_dist38, ArchEv_dist39,
                   ArchEv_dist40, ArchEv_dist41,
                   ArchEv_dist42, ArchEv_dist43,
                   ArchEv_dist44, ArchEv_dist45,
                   ArchEv_dist46, ArchEv_dist47,
                   ArchEv_dist48, ArchEv_dist49,
                   ArchEv_dist50, ArchEv_dist51,
                   ArchEv_dist52, ArchEv_dist53,
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SubCat_dist988 ,
SubCat_dist989 ,
SubCat_dist990 ,
SubCat_dist991 ,
SubCat_dist992 ,
SubCat_dist993 ,
SubCat_dist994 ,
SubCat_dist995 ,
SubCat_dist996 ,
SubCat_dist997 ,
#SubCat_dist998 ,
SubCat_dist999 ,
SubCat_dist1000,
SubCat_dist1001,
SubCat_dist1002,
SubCat_dist1003,
SubCat_dist1004,
SubCat_dist1005,
SubCat_dist1006,
SubCat_dist1007,
SubCat_dist1008,
SubCat_dist1009,
SubCat_dist1010,
SubCat_dist1011,
SubCat_dist1012,
SubCat_dist1013,
SubCat_dist1014,
SubCat_dist1015,
SubCat_dist1016,
SubCat_dist1017,
SubCat_dist1018,
SubCat_dist1019,
SubCat_dist1020,
SubCat_dist1021,
SubCat_dist1022,
SubCat_dist1023,
SubCat_dist1024,
SubCat_dist1025,
SubCat_dist1026,
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SubCat_dist1031,
SubCat_dist1032,
#SubCat_dist1033,
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SubCat_dist1035,
SubCat_dist1036,
SubCat_dist1037,
SubCat_dist1038,
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SubCat_dist1064,
SubCat_dist1065,
SubCat_dist1066,
SubCat_dist1067,
#SubCat_dist1068,
SubCat_dist1069,
SubCat_dist1070,
SubCat_dist1071,
SubCat_dist1072,
SubCat_dist1073,
SubCat_dist1074,
SubCat_dist1075,
SubCat_dist1076,
SubCat_dist1077,
SubCat_dist1078,
SubCat_dist1079,
SubCat_dist1080,
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SubCat_dist1083,
SubCat_dist1084,
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SubCat_dist1093,
SubCat_dist1094,
SubCat_dist1095,
SubCat_dist1096,
SubCat_dist1097,
SubCat_dist1098,
SubCat_dist1099,
SubCat_dist1100,
SubCat_dist1101,
SubCat_dist1102,
#SubCat_dist1103,
SubCat_dist1104,
SubCat_dist1105,
SubCat_dist1106,
SubCat_dist1107,
SubCat_dist1108,
SubCat_dist1109,
SubCat_dist1110,
SubCat_dist1111,
SubCat_dist1112,
SubCat_dist1113,
SubCat_dist1114,
SubCat_dist1115,
SubCat_dist1116,
SubCat_dist1117,
SubCat_dist1118,
SubCat_dist1119,
SubCat_dist1120,
SubCat_dist1121,
SubCat_dist1122,
SubCat_dist1123,
SubCat_dist1124,
SubCat_dist1125,
SubCat_dist1126,
SubCat_dist1127,
SubCat_dist1128,
SubCat_dist1129,
SubCat_dist1130,

```
SubCat_dist1131,  
SubCat_dist1132,  
SubCat_dist1133,  
SubCat_dist1134,  
SubCat_dist1135,  
SubCat_dist1136,  
SubCat_dist1137,  
#SubCat_dist1138,  
SubCat_dist1139,  
SubCat_dist1140,  
SubCat_dist1141,  
SubCat_dist1142,  
SubCat_dist1143,  
SubCat_dist1144,  
SubCat_dist1145,  
SubCat_dist1146,  
SubCat_dist1147,  
SubCat_dist1148,  
SubCat_dist1149,  
SubCat_dist1150,  
SubCat_dist1151,  
SubCat_dist1152,  
SubCat_dist1153,  
SubCat_dist1154,  
SubCat_dist1155)
```

```
write.xlsx(ArchEv_dist, file="./4result/Tables/100AD/Arch_Evidence_Distances.xlsx")
```

```
#####  
#=====
```

```
#SECOND ORDER EFFECTS
```

```
#=====
```

```
#####
```

```
#####Agricultural Installations#####
```

```
#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
```

```
a.nn <- nndist(X = a.pp)
```

```
str(a.nn)
```

```
mean(a.nn)
```

```
AgriculturalInstallations<- a.nn
```

```
plot(hist(AgriculturalInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Installations")
```

```
abline(v=mean(a.nn))
```

```
abline(v=median(a.nn), lty=2)
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_a.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
```

```
plot(hist(AgriculturalInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Installations")
```

```
abline(v=mean(a.nn))
```

```
abline(v=median(a.nn), lty=2)
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
```

```
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((a.pp$n/area.sqm)))
```

```
nnE
```

```
R.g <- mean(a.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
```

```
R.g
```

```
mean_a.nn<- mean(a.nn)
```

```
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_a.nn)
```

```
names(table) <- c("R Value_a.pp", "Mean NN Dist a.pp")
```

```
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_a.pp.xlsx")
```

```
#####
```

```
#G-Function
```

```
#####
```

```
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
```

```
sites.g <- Gest(a.pp)
```

```
plot(sites.g)
```

```
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
gfunction <- envelope(a.pp,  
                      fun = Gest,  
                      nsim = 10)
```

```
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Installations")
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_a.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
```

```
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Installations")
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
#####
```

```
#F-Function
```

```
#####
```

```
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
ffunction <- envelope(a.pp,  
                      fun = Fest,  
                      nsim = 10)
```

```
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Installations")
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_a.pp.pdf")
```

```

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(a.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_a.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(a.pp,
                      fun = Lest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_a.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Installations")
dev.off()

#####Agricultural Processing Installations#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
a_1.nn <- nndist(X = a_1.pp)

str(a_1.nn)
mean(a_1.nn)
AgriculturalProcessingInstallations<- a_1.nn
plot(hist(AgriculturalProcessingInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Processing
Installations")
abline(v=mean(a_1.nn))
abline(v=median(a_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_a_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(AgriculturalProcessingInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Processing
Installations")
abline(v=mean(a_1.nn))
abline(v=median(a_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((a_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(a_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_a_1.nn<- mean(a_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_a_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_a_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist a_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_a_1.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(a_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(a_1.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_a_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(a_1.pp,
                      fun = Fest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_a_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function

```

```

#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(a_1.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_a_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(a_1.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_a_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Processing Installations")
dev.off()

#####Agricultural Storing Installations#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
a_2.nn <- nndist(X = a_2.pp)

str(a_2.nn)
mean(a_2.nn)
AgriculturalStoringInstallations<- a_2.nn
plot(hist(AgriculturalStoringInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Storing
Installations")
abline(v=mean(a_2.nn))
abline(v=median(a_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_a_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(AgriculturalStoringInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Storing
Installations")
abline(v=mean(a_2.nn))
abline(v=median(a_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((a_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(a_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_a_2.nn<- mean(a_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_a_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_a_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist a_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_a_2.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(a_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(a_2.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_a_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(a_2.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_a_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

```

```

kfunction <- envelope(a_2.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_a_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(a_2.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_a_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Storing Installations")
dev.off()

#####Agricultural Terraces/ Fields#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
a_3.nn <- nndist(X = a_3.pp)

str(a_3.nn)
mean(a_3.nn)
AgriculturalTerraces/Fields<- a_3.nn
plot(hist(AgriculturalTerraces/Fields), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
abline(v=mean(a_3.nn))
abline(v=median(a_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_a_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(AgriculturalTerraces/Fields), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
abline(v=mean(a_3.nn))
abline(v=median(a_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((a_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(a_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_a_3.nn<- mean(a_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_a_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_a_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist a_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_a_3.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(a_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(a_3.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_a_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(a_3.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_a_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(a_3.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_a_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")

```

```

dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(a_3.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_a_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Agricultural Terraces/ Fields")
dev.off()

#####Communication Infrastructures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
b.nn <- nndist(X = b.pp)

str(b.nn)
mean(b.nn)
CommunicationInfrastructures<- b.nn
plot(hist(CommunicationInfrastructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Communication Infrastructures")
abline(v=mean(b.nn))
abline(v=median(b.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_b.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(CommunicationInfrastructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Communication Infrastructures")
abline(v=mean(b.nn))
abline(v=median(b.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((b.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(b.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_b.nn<- mean(b.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_b.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_b.pp", "Mean NN Dist b.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_b.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(b.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(b.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_b.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Communication Infrastructures")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(b.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_b.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Communication Infrastructures")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(b.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_b.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Communication Infrastructures")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(b.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

```

```

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Communication Infrastructures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_b.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Communication Infrastructures")
dev.off()

```

```
#####Caravanserais#####
```

```
#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
```

```
b_1.nn <- nndist(X = b_1.pp)
```

```
str(b_1.nn)
```

```
mean(b_1.nn)
```

```
Caravanserais<- b_1.nn
```

```
plot(hist(Caravanserais), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Caravanserais")
```

```
abline(v=mean(b_1.nn))
```

```
abline(v=median(b_1.nn), lty=2)
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_b_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
```

```
plot(hist(Caravanserais), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Caravanserais")
```

```
abline(v=mean(b_1.nn))
```

```
abline(v=median(b_1.nn), lty=2)
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
```

```
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((b_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
```

```
nnE
```

```
R.g <- mean(b_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
```

```
R.g
```

```
mean_b_1.nn<- mean(b_1.nn)
```

```
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_b_1.nn)
```

```
names(table) <- c("R Value_b_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist_b_1.pp")
```

```
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_b_1.pp.xlsx")
```

```
#####
```

```
#G-Function
```

```
#####
```

```
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
```

```
sites.g <- Gest(b_1.pp)
```

```
plot(sites.g)
```

```
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
gfunction <- envelope(b_1.pp,
```

```
fun = Gest,
```

```
nsim = 10)
```

```
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_b_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
```

```
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
#####
```

```
#F-Function
```

```
#####
```

```
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
ffunction <- envelope(b_1.pp,
```

```
fun = Fest,
```

```
nsim = 10)
```

```
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_b_1.pp.pdf")
```

```
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
#####
```

```
#K-Function
```

```
#####
```

```
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
kfunction <- envelope(b_1.pp,
```

```
fun = Kest,
```

```
nsim = 10)
```

```
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_b_1.pp.pdf")
```

```
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
#####
```

```
#L-Function
```

```
#####
```

```
lfunction <- envelope(b_1.pp,
```

```
fun = Lest,
```

```
nsim = 10)
```

```
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_b_1.pp.pdf")
```

```
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Caravanserais")
```

```
dev.off()
```

```

#####Road Markers#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
b_2.nn <- nndist(X = b_2.pp)

str(b_2.nn)
mean(b_2.nn)
RoadMarkers<- b_2.nn
plot(hist(RoadMarkers), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Road Markers")
abline(v=mean(b_2.nn))
abline(v=median(b_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_b_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(RoadMarkers), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Road Markers")
abline(v=mean(b_2.nn))
abline(v=median(b_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((b_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(b_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_b_2.nn<- mean(b_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_b_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_b_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist b_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_b_2.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(b_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(b_2.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Road Markers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_b_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Road Markers")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(b_2.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Road Markers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_b_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Road Markers")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(b_2.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Road Markers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_b_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Road Markers")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(b_2.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Road Markers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_b_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Road Markers")
dev.off()

#####Road Stations#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
b_3.nn <- nndist(X = b_3.pp)

```

```

str(b_3.nn)
mean(b_3.nn)
RoadStations<- b_3.nn
plot(hist(RoadStations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Road Stations")
abline(v=mean(b_3.nn))
abline(v=median(b_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_b_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(RoadStations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Road Stations")
abline(v=mean(b_3.nn))
abline(v=median(b_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((b_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(b_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_b_3.nn<- mean(b_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_b_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_b_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist_b_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_b_3.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(b_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(b_3.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Road Stations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_b_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Road Stations")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(b_3.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Road Stations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_b_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Road Stations")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(b_3.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Road Stations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_b_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Road Stations")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(b_3.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Road Stations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_b_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Road Stations")
dev.off()

#####Roads#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
b_4.nn <- nndist(X = b_4.pp)

str(b_4.nn)
mean(b_4.nn)
Roads<- b_4.nn
plot(hist(Roads), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Roads")
abline(v=mean(b_4.nn))
abline(v=median(b_4.nn), lty=2)

```

```

pdf("../5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_b_4.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Roads), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Roads")
abline(v=mean(b_4.nn))
abline(v=median(b_4.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((b_4.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(b_4.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_b_4.nn<- mean(b_4.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_b_4.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_b_4.pp", "Mean NN Dist b_4.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "../4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_b_4.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(b_4.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(b_4.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Roads")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/G-function_b_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Roads")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(b_4.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Roads")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/F-function_b_4.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Roads")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(b_4.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Roads")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/K-function_b_4.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Roads")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(b_4.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Roads")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/L-function_b_4.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Roads")
dev.off()

#####Routes/ Tracks (naqb)#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
b_5.nn <- nndist(X = b_5.pp)

str(b_5.nn)
mean(b_5.nn)
Routes/Tracks(naqb)<- b_5.nn
plot(hist(Routes/Tracks(naqb)), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
abline(v=mean(b_5.nn))
abline(v=median(b_5.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_b_5.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Routes/Tracks(naqb)), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
abline(v=mean(b_5.nn))
abline(v=median(b_5.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

```

```

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((b_5.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(b_5.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_b_5.nn<- mean(b_5.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_b_5.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_b_5.pp", "Mean NN Dist b_5.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_b_5.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(b_5.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(b_5.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_b_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(b_5.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_b_5.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(b_5.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_b_5.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(b_5.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_b_5.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Routes/ Tracks (naqb)")
dev.off()

#####Exploitation/ Industrial Sites#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
c.nn <- nndist(X = c.pp)

str(c.nn)
mean(c.nn)
Exploitation/IndustrialSites<- c.nn
plot(hist(Exploitation/IndustrialSites), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
abline(v=mean(c.nn))
abline(v=median(c.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_c.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Exploitation/IndustrialSites), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
abline(v=mean(c.nn))
abline(v=median(c.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((c.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(c.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_c.nn<- mean(c.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_c.nn)

```

```

names(table) <- c("R Value_c.pp", "Mean NN Dist c.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_c.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(c.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(c.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_c.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(c.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_c.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(c.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_c.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(c.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_c.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Exploitation/ Industrial Sites")
dev.off()

#####Industrial/ Exploitation Installations#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
c_1.nn <- nndist(X = c_1.pp)

str(c_1.nn)
mean(c_1.nn)
Industrial/ExploitationInstallations<- c_1.nn
plot(hist(Industrial/ExploitationInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Industrial/ Exploitation
Installations")
abline(v=mean(c_1.nn))
abline(v=median(c_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_c_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Industrial/ExploitationInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Industrial/ Exploitation
Installations")
abline(v=mean(c_1.nn))
abline(v=median(c_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((c_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(c_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_c_1.nn<- mean(c_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_c_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_c_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist c_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_c_1.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function

```

```

#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(c_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(c_1.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_c_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(c_1.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_c_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(c_1.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_c_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(c_1.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_c_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Industrial/ Exploitation Installations")
dev.off()

#####Funerary and Commemorative Structures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
d.nn <- nndist(X = d.pp)

str(d.nn)
mean(d.nn)
FuneraryandCommemorativeStructures<- d.nn
plot(hist(FuneraryandCommemorativeStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Funerary and Commemorative
Structures")
abline(v=mean(d.nn))
abline(v=median(d.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_d.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(FuneraryandCommemorativeStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Funerary and Commemorative
Structures")
abline(v=mean(d.nn))
abline(v=median(d.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((d.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(d.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_d.nn<- mean(d.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_d.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_d.pp", "Mean NN Dist d.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_d.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(d.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

```

```

gfunction <- envelope(d.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_d.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(d.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_d.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(d.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_d.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(d.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_d.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Funerary and Commemorative Structures")
dev.off()

#####Cemeteries#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
d_1.nn <- nndist(X = d_1.pp)

str(d_1.nn)
mean(d_1.nn)
Cemeteries<- d_1.nn
plot(hist(Cemeteries), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Cemeteries")
abline(v=mean(d_1.nn))
abline(v=median(d_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_d_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Cemeteries), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Cemeteries")
abline(v=mean(d_1.nn))
abline(v=median(d_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((d_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(d_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_d_1.nn<- mean(d_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_d_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_d_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist d_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_d_1.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(d_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(d_1.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_d_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Cemeteries")

```

```

dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(d_1.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_d_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Cemeteries")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(d_1.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_d_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Cemeteries")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(d_1.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Cemeteries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_d_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Cemeteries")
dev.off()

#####Isolated Funerary Monuments#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
d_2.nn <- nndist(X = d_2.pp)

str(d_2.nn)
mean(d_2.nn)
IsolatedFuneraryMonuments<- d_2.nn
plot(hist(IsolatedFuneraryMonuments), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Isolated Funerary Monuments")
abline(v=mean(d_2.nn))
abline(v=median(d_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_d_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(IsolatedFuneraryMonuments), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Isolated Funerary Monuments")
abline(v=mean(d_2.nn))
abline(v=median(d_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((d_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(d_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_d_2.nn<- mean(d_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_d_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_d_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist d_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_d_2.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(d_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(d_2.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_d_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(d_2.pp,
                    fun = Fest,

```

```

nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_d_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(d_2.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_d_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(d_2.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_d_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Isolated Funerary Monuments")
dev.off()

#####Military Structures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
e.nn <- nndist(X = e.pp)

str(e.nn)
mean(e.nn)
MilitaryStructures<- e.nn
plot(hist(MilitaryStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Military Structures")
abline(v=mean(e.nn))
abline(v=median(e.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_e.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(MilitaryStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Military Structures")
abline(v=mean(e.nn))
abline(v=median(e.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((e.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(e.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_e.nn<- mean(e.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_e.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_e.pp", "Mean NN Dist e.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_e.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(e.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(e.pp,
                     fun = Gest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_e.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Military Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(e.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_e.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Military Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####

```

```

#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(e.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_e.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Military Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(e.pp,
                      fun = Lest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Military Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_e.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Military Structures")
dev.off()

#####Forts#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
e_1.nn <- nndist(X = e_1.pp)

str(e_1.nn)
mean(e_1.nn)
Forts<- e_1.nn
plot(hist(Forts), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Forts")
abline(v=mean(e_1.nn))
abline(v=median(e_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_e_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Forts), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Forts")
abline(v=mean(e_1.nn))
abline(v=median(e_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((e_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(e_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_e_1.nn<- mean(e_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_e_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_e_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist e_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_e_1.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(e_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(e_1.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Forts")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_e_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Forts")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(e_1.pp,
                      fun = Fest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Forts")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_e_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Forts")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(e_1.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Forts")

```

```

pdf("../5pictures/100AD/K-function_e_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Forts")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(e_1.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Forts")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/L-function_e_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Forts")
dev.off()

#####Fortlets#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
e_2.nn <- nndist(X = e_2.pp)

str(e_2.nn)
mean(e_2.nn)
Fortlets<- e_2.nn
plot(hist(Fortlets), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Fortlets")
abline(v=mean(e_2.nn))
abline(v=median(e_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_e_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Fortlets), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Fortlets")
abline(v=mean(e_2.nn))
abline(v=median(e_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((e_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(e_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_e_2.nn<- mean(e_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_e_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_e_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist e_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_e_2.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(e_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(e_2.pp,
                     fun = Gest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Fortlets")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/G-function_e_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Fortlets")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(e_2.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Fortlets")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/F-function_e_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Fortlets")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(e_2.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Fortlets")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/K-function_e_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Fortlets")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####

```

```

lfunction <- envelope(e_2.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Fortlets")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_e_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Fortlets")
dev.off()

#####Fortresses#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
e_3.nn <- nndist(X = e_3.pp)

str(e_3.nn)
mean(e_3.nn)
Fortresses<- e_3.nn
plot(hist(Fortresses), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Fortresses")
abline(v=mean(e_3.nn))
abline(v=median(e_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_e_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Fortresses), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Fortresses")
abline(v=mean(e_3.nn))
abline(v=median(e_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((e_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(e_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_e_3.nn<- mean(e_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_e_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_e_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist e_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_e_3.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(e_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(e_3.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_e_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Fortresses")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(e_3.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_e_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Fortresses")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(e_3.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_e_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Fortresses")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(e_3.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Fortresses")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_e_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Fortresses")

```

```

dev.off()

#####Watchtowers#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
e_4.nn <- nndist(X = e_4.pp)

str(e_4.nn)
mean(e_4.nn)
Watchtowers<- e_4.nn
plot(hist(Watchtowers), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Watchtowers")
abline(v=mean(e_4.nn))
abline(v=median(e_4.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_e_4.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Watchtowers), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Watchtowers")
abline(v=mean(e_4.nn))
abline(v=median(e_4.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((e_4.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(e_4.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_e_4.nn<- mean(e_4.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_e_4.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_e_4.pp", "Mean NN Dist e_4.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_e_4.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(e_4.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(e_4.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_e_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Watchtowers")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(e_4.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_e_4.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Watchtowers")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(e_4.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_e_4.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Watchtowers")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(e_4.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Watchtowers")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_e_4.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Watchtowers")
dev.off()

#####Religious Structures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:

```

```

f.nn <- nndist(X = f.pp)

str(f.nn)
mean(f.nn)
ReligiousStructures<- f.nn
plot(hist(ReligiousStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Religious Structures")
abline(v=mean(f.nn))
abline(v=median(f.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_f.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(ReligiousStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Religious Structures")
abline(v=mean(f.nn))
abline(v=median(f.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((f.pp$N/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(f.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_f.nn<- mean(f.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_f.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_f.pp", "Mean NN Dist f.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_f.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(f.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(f.pp,
                     fun = Gest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_f.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Religious Structures")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(f.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_f.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Religious Structures")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(f.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_f.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Religious Structures")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(f.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Religious Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_f.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Religious Structures")
dev.off()

#####Isolated Cultic Installation#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
f_1.nn <- nndist(X = f_1.pp)

str(f_1.nn)
mean(f_1.nn)
IsolatedCulticInstallation<- f_1.nn
plot(hist(IsolatedCulticInstallation), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Isolated Cultic Installation")
abline(v=mean(f_1.nn))

```

```

abline(v=median(f_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_f_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(IsolatedCulticInstallation), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Isolated Cultic Installation")
abline(v=mean(f_1.nn))
abline(v=median(f_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((f_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(f_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_f_1.nn<- mean(f_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_f_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_f_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist_f_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_f_1.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(f_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(f_1.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_f_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(f_1.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_f_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(f_1.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_f_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(f_1.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_f_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Isolated Cultic Installation")
dev.off()

#####Sanctuaries#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
f_2.nn <- nndist(X = f_2.pp)

str(f_2.nn)
mean(f_2.nn)
Sanctuaries<- f_2.nn
plot(hist(Sanctuaries), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Sanctuaries")
abline(v=mean(f_2.nn))
abline(v=median(f_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_f_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Sanctuaries), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Sanctuaries")
abline(v=mean(f_2.nn))
abline(v=median(f_2.nn), lty=2)

```

```

dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((f_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(f_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_f_2.nn<- mean(f_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_f_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_f_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist f_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_f_2.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(f_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(f_2.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_f_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(f_2.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_f_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(f_2.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_f_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Sanctuaries")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(f_2.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Sanctuaries")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_f_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Sanctuaries")
dev.off()

#####Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
f_3.nn <- nndist(X = f_3.pp)

str(f_3.nn)
mean(f_3.nn)
SignificantReligious/CulticStructures<- f_3.nn
plot(hist(SignificantReligious/CulticStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Significant Religious/
Cultic Structures")
abline(v=mean(f_3.nn))
abline(v=median(f_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_f_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(SignificantReligious/CulticStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Significant Religious/
Cultic Structures")
abline(v=mean(f_3.nn))
abline(v=median(f_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((f_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))

```

```

nnE
R.g <- mean(f_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_f_3.nn<- mean(f_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_f_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_f_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist f_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_f_3.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(f_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(f_3.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_f_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(f_3.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_f_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(f_3.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_f_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(f_3.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_f_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Significant Religious/ Cultic Structures")
dev.off()

#####Settlements#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g.nn <- nndist(X = g.pp)

str(g.nn)
mean(g.nn)
Settlements<- g.nn
plot(hist(Settlements), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Settlements")
abline(v=mean(g.nn))
abline(v=median(g.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Settlements), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Settlements")
abline(v=mean(g.nn))
abline(v=median(g.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g.pp$N/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g.nn<- mean(g.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g.pp", "Mean NN Dist g.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g.pp.xlsx")

```

```

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(g.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_g.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Settlements")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(g.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_g.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Settlements")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(g.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_g.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Settlements")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(g.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Settlements")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_g.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Settlements")
dev.off()

#####Cities#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g_1.nn <- nndist(X = g_1.pp)

str(g_1.nn)
mean(g_1.nn)
Cities<- g_1.nn
plot(hist(Cities), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Cities")
abline(v=mean(g_1.nn))
abline(v=median(g_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Cities), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Cities")
abline(v=mean(g_1.nn))
abline(v=median(g_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g_1.pp$N/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g_1.nn<- mean(g_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist g_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g_1.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)

```

```

# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(g_1.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_g_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Cities")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(g_1.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_g_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Cities")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(g_1.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_g_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Cities")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(g_1.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Cities")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_g_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Cities")
dev.off()

#####Cluster of Building Structures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g_2.nn <- nndist(X = g_2.pp)

str(g_2.nn)
mean(g_2.nn)
ClusterofBuildingStructures<- g_2.nn
plot(hist(ClusterofBuildingStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Cluster of Building Structures")
abline(v=mean(g_2.nn))
abline(v=median(g_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(ClusterofBuildingStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Cluster of Building Structures")
abline(v=mean(g_2.nn))
abline(v=median(g_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g_2.nn<- mean(g_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist_g_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g_2.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(g_2.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Cluster of Building Structures")

```

```

pdf("../5pictures/100AD/G-function_g_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(g_2.pp,
                      fun = Fest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/F-function_g_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
kfunction <- envelope(g_2.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/K-function_g_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(g_2.pp,
                      fun = Lest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/L-function_g_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Cluster of Building Structures")
dev.off()

#####Farms#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g_3.nn <- nndist(X = g_3.pp)

str(g_3.nn)
mean(g_3.nn)
Farms<- g_3.nn
plot(hist(Farms), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Farms")
abline(v=mean(g_3.nn))
abline(v=median(g_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Farms), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Farms")
abline(v=mean(g_3.nn))
abline(v=median(g_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g_3.nn<- mean(g_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist g_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "../4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g_3.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
gfunction <- envelope(g_3.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Farms")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/G-function_g_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Farms")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

```

```

ffunction <- envelope(g_3.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_g_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Farms")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(g_3.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_g_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Farms")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(g_3.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Farms")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_g_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Farms")
dev.off()

#####Towns#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g_4.nn <- nndist(X = g_4.pp)

str(g_4.nn)
mean(g_4.nn)
Towns<- g_4.nn
plot(hist(Towns), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Towns")
abline(v=mean(g_4.nn))
abline(v=median(g_4.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g_4.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Towns), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Towns")
abline(v=mean(g_4.nn))
abline(v=median(g_4.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g_4.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g_4.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g_4.nn<- mean(g_4.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g_4.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g_4.pp", "Mean NN Dist g_4.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".\\4result\\Tables\\100AD\\Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g_4.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g_4.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(g_4.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Towns")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_g_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Towns")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(g_4.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Towns")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_g_4.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Towns")

```

```

dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(g_4.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Towns")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/K-function_g_4.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Towns")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(g_4.pp,
                      fun = Lest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Towns")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/L-function_g_4.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Towns")
dev.off()

#####Villae#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g_5.nn <- nndist(X = g_5.pp)

str(g_5.nn)
mean(g_5.nn)
Villae<- g_5.nn
plot(hist(Villae), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Villae")
abline(v=mean(g_5.nn))
abline(v=median(g_5.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g_5.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Villae), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Villae")
abline(v=mean(g_5.nn))
abline(v=median(g_5.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g_5.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g_5.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g_5.nn<- mean(g_5.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g_5.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g_5.pp", "Mean NN Dist g_5.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "../4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g_5.pp.xlsx")
#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g_5.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(g_5.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Villae")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/G-function_g_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Villae")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(g_5.pp,
                      fun = Fest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Villae")
pdf("../5pictures/100AD/F-function_g_5.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Villae")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

```

```

kfunction <- envelope(g_5.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Villae")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_g_5.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Villae")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(g_5.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Villae")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_g_5.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Villae")
dev.off()

######Villages#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
g_6.nn <- nndist(X = g_6.pp)

str(g_6.nn)
mean(g_6.nn)
Villages<- g_6.nn
plot(hist(Villages), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Villages")
abline(v=mean(g_6.nn))
abline(v=median(g_6.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_g_6.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Villages), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Villages")
abline(v=mean(g_6.nn))
abline(v=median(g_6.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((g_6.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(g_6.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_g_6.nn<- mean(g_6.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_g_6.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_g_6.pp", "Mean NN Dist g_6.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_g_6.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(g_6.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(g_6.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_g_6.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Villages")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(g_6.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_g_6.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Villages")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(g_6.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_g_6.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Villages")
dev.off()

```

```

#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(g_6.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Villages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_g_6.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Villages")
dev.off()

#####Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
h.nn <- nndist(X = h.pp)

str(h.nn)
mean(h.nn)
UnspecifiedStructuresand/orFeatures<- h.nn
plot(hist(UnspecifiedStructuresand/orFeatures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Unspecified Structure(s)
and/ or Feature(s)")
abline(v=mean(h.nn))
abline(v=median(h.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_h.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(UnspecifiedStructuresand/orFeatures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Unspecified Structure(s)
and/ or Feature(s)")
abline(v=mean(h.nn))
abline(v=median(h.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((h.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(h.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_h.nn<- mean(h.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_h.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_h.pp", "Mean NN Dist h.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_h.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(h.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(h.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_h.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(h.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_h.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(h.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_h.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(h.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)

```

```
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_h.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Unspecified Structure(s) and/ or Feature(s)")
dev.off()
```

```
#####Epigraphical Sites or Locations#####
```

```
#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
h_1.nn <- nndist(X = h_1.pp)
```

```
str(h_1.nn)
mean(h_1.nn)
EpigraphicalSitesorLocations<- h_1.nn
plot(hist(EpigraphicalSitesorLocations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
abline(v=mean(h_1.nn))
abline(v=median(h_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_h_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(EpigraphicalSitesorLocations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
abline(v=mean(h_1.nn))
abline(v=median(h_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()
```

```
#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((h_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(h_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_h_1.nn<- mean(h_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_h_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_h_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist_h_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_h_1.pp.xlsx")
```

```
#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(h_1.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
gfunction <- envelope(h_1.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_h_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
```

```
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(h_1.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_h_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
```

```
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
```

```
kfunction <- envelope(h_1.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_h_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
```

```
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(h_1.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_h_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Epigraphical Sites or Locations")
dev.off()
```

```
#####Find Clusters#####
```

```

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
h_2.nn <- nndist(X = h_2.pp)

str(h_2.nn)
mean(h_2.nn)
FindClusters<- h_2.nn
plot(hist(FindClusters), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Find Clusters")
abline(v=mean(h_2.nn))
abline(v=median(h_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_h_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(FindClusters), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Find Clusters")
abline(v=mean(h_2.nn))
abline(v=median(h_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((h_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(h_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_h_2.nn<- mean(h_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_h_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_h_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist h_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "../4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_h_2.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(h_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(h_2.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Find Clusters")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/G-function_h_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Find Clusters")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(h_2.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Find Clusters")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/F-function_h_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Find Clusters")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(h_2.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Find Clusters")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/K-function_h_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Find Clusters")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(h_2.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Find Clusters")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/L-function_h_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Find Clusters")
dev.off()

#####Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
h_3.nn <- nndist(X = h_3.pp)

str(h_3.nn)
mean(h_3.nn)
Naturaland/orRock-cutStructuresofUndeterminedFunction<- h_3.nn

```

```

plot(hist(Naturaland/orRock-cutStructuresofUndeterminedFunction), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Natural
and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
abline(v=mean(h_3.nn))
abline(v=median(h_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_h_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Naturaland/orRock-cutStructuresofUndeterminedFunction), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Natural
and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
abline(v=mean(h_3.nn))
abline(v=median(h_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((h_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(h_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_h_3.nn<- mean(h_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_h_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_h_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist h_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_h_3.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(h_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(h_3.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_h_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(h_3.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_h_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(h_3.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_h_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(h_3.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_h_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Natural and/ or Rock-cut Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()

#####Structure(s) of Undetermined Function#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
h_4.nn <- nndist(X = h_4.pp)

str(h_4.nn)
mean(h_4.nn)
StructuresofUndeterminedFunction<- h_4.nn
plot(hist(StructuresofUndeterminedFunction), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Structure(s) of Undetermined
Function")
abline(v=mean(h_4.nn))
abline(v=median(h_4.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_h_4.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as

```

```

pdf
plot(hist(StructuresofUndeterminedFunction), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Structure(s) of Undetermined
Function")
abline(v=mean(h_4.nn))
abline(v=median(h_4.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((h_4.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(h_4.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_h_4.nn<- mean(h_4.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_h_4.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_h_4.pp", "Mean NN Dist h_4.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_h_4.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(h_4.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(h_4.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_h_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(h_4.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_h_4.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(h_4.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_h_4.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(h_4.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_h_4.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Structure(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()

#####Wall(s) of Undetermined Function#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
h_5.nn <- nndist(X = h_5.pp)

str(h_5.nn)
mean(h_5.nn)
WallsofUndeterminedFunction<- h_5.nn
plot(hist(WallsofUndeterminedFunction), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
abline(v=mean(h_5.nn))
abline(v=median(h_5.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_h_5.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(WallsofUndeterminedFunction), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
abline(v=mean(h_5.nn))
abline(v=median(h_5.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

```

```

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((h_5.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(h_5.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_h_5.nn<- mean(h_5.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_h_5.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_h_5.pp", "Mean NN Dist h_5.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_h_5.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(h_5.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(h_5.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_h_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(h_5.pp,
                      fun = Fest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_h_5.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(h_5.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_h_5.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(h_5.pp,
                      fun = Lest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_h_5.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Wall(s) of Undetermined Function")
dev.off()

#####Water Structures#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
i.nn <- nndist(X = i.pp)

str(i.nn)
mean(i.nn)
WaterStructures<- i.nn
plot(hist(WaterStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Water Structures")
abline(v=mean(i.nn))
abline(v=median(i.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_i.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(WaterStructures), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Water Structures")
abline(v=mean(i.nn))
abline(v=median(i.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((i.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(i.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_i.nn<- mean(i.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_i.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_i.pp", "Mean NN Dist i.pp")

```

```

write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_i.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(i.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(i.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_i.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Water Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(i.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_i.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Water Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(i.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_i.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Water Structures")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(i.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Water Structures")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_i.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Water Structures")
dev.off()

#####Dams/ Barrages#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
i_1.nn <- nndist(X = i_1.pp)

str(i_1.nn)
mean(i_1.nn)
Dams/Barrages<- i_1.nn
plot(hist(Dams/Barrages), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Dams/ Barrages")
abline(v=mean(i_1.nn))
abline(v=median(i_1.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_i_1.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Dams/Barrages), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Dams/ Barrages")
abline(v=mean(i_1.nn))
abline(v=median(i_1.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((i_1.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(i_1.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_i_1.nn<- mean(i_1.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_i_1.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_i_1.pp", "Mean NN Dist i_1.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_i_1.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(i_1.pp)

```

```

plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(i_1.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_i_1.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Dams/ Barrages")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(i_1.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_i_1.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Dams/ Barrages")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(i_1.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_i_1.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Dams/ Barrages")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(i_1.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Dams/ Barrages")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_i_1.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Dams/ Barrages")
dev.off()

#####Ssprings#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
i_2.nn <- nndist(X = i_2.pp)

str(i_2.nn)
mean(i_2.nn)
Springs<- i_2.nn
plot(hist(Springs), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Springs")
abline(v=mean(i_2.nn))
abline(v=median(i_2.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_i_2.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(Springs), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Springs")
abline(v=mean(i_2.nn))
abline(v=median(i_2.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((i_2.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(i_2.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_i_2.nn<- mean(i_2.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_i_2.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_i_2.pp", "Mean NN Dist i_2.pp")
write.xlsx(table, ".4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_i_2.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(i_2.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(i_2.pp,
                     fun = Gest,
                     nsim = 10)

```

```

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_i_2.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Springs")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(i_2.pp,
                      fun = Fest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/F-function_i_2.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Springs")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(i_2.pp,
                      fun = Kest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_i_2.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Springs")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(i_2.pp,
                      fun = Lest,
                      nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Springs")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_i_2.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Springs")
dev.off()

#####Water Conduits#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
i_3.nn <- nndist(X = i_3.pp)

str(i_3.nn)
mean(i_3.nn)
WaterConduits<- i_3.nn
plot(hist(WaterConduits), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Water Conduits")
abline(v=mean(i_3.nn))
abline(v=median(i_3.nn), lty=2)
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_i_3.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(WaterConduits), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Water Conduits")
abline(v=mean(i_3.nn))
abline(v=median(i_3.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((i_3.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(i_3.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_i_3.nn<- mean(i_3.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_i_3.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_i_3.pp", "Mean NN Dist i_3.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "./4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_i_3.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(i_3.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(i_3.pp,
                      fun = Gest,
                      nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Water Conduits")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/G-function_i_3.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Water Conduits")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####

```

```

##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(i_3.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Water Conduits")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/F-function_i_3.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Water Conduits")
dev.off()
#####
#K-Function
#####
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(i_3.pp,
                    fun = Kest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Water Conduits")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/K-function_i_3.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Water Conduits")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(i_3.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Water Conduits")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/L-function_i_3.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Water Conduits")
dev.off()

#####Water Storage Installations#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
i_4.nn <- nndist(X = i_4.pp)

str(i_4.nn)
mean(i_4.nn)
WaterStorageInstallations<- i_4.nn
plot(hist(WaterStorageInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Water Storage Installations")
abline(v=mean(i_4.nn))
abline(v=median(i_4.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_i_4.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as pdf
plot(hist(WaterStorageInstallations), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Water Storage Installations")
abline(v=mean(i_4.nn))
abline(v=median(i_4.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((i_4.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(i_4.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_i_4.nn<- mean(i_4.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_i_4.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_i_4.pp", "Mean NN Dist i_4.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "../4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_i_4.pp.xlsx")

#####
#G-Function
#####
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(i_4.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(i_4.pp,
                    fun = Gest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Water Storage Installations")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/G-function_i_4.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()
#####
#F-Function
#####
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(i_4.pp,
                    fun = Fest,
                    nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Water Storage Installations")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/F-function_i_4.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Water Storage Installations")

```

```

dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(i_4.pp,
                     fun = Kest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Water Storage Installations")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/K-function_i_4.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()
#=====
#L-Function
#=====
lfunction <- envelope(i_4.pp,
                     fun = Lest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Water Storage Installations")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/L-function_i_4.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Water Storage Installations")
dev.off()

#####Wells#####

#Nearest Neighbour Distance:
i_5.nn <- nndist(X = i_5.pp)

str(i_5.nn)
mean(i_5.nn)
Wells<- i_5.nn
plot(hist(Wells), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Wells")
abline(v=mean(i_5.nn))
abline(v=median(i_5.nn), lty=2)
pdf("../pictures/100AD/Nearest Neighbor Distances_i_5.pp.pdf", height=4, width=6, bg="white") # plot cov_compare as
pdf
plot(hist(Wells), main= "Nearest Neighbor Distances Between Wells")
abline(v=mean(i_5.nn))
abline(v=median(i_5.nn), lty=2)
dev.off()

#Nearest neighbor Distance - Clark and Evans' R:
nnE <- 1/(2*sqrt((i_5.pp$n/area.sqm)))
nnE
R.g <- mean(i_5.nn)/nnE #R<1: more clustered; R>1:more evenly spaced
R.g
mean_i_5.nn<- mean(i_5.nn)
table<-data.frame(R.g, mean_i_5.nn)
names(table) <- c("R Value_i_5.pp", "Mean NN Dist i_5.pp")
write.xlsx(table, "../4result/Tables/100AD/Rvalues_MeanNNDist_i_5.pp.xlsx")

#=====
#G-Function
#=====
#First approach based on theoretical assumptions, i.e. CSR:
sites.g <- Gest(i_5.pp)
plot(sites.g)
# Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

gfunction <- envelope(i_5.pp,
                     fun = Gest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Wells")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/G-function_i_5.pp.pdf", height=6, width=10, bg="white")
plot(gfunction, main= "G-function of Wells")
dev.off()
#=====
#F-Function
#=====
##Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR
ffunction <- envelope(i_5.pp,
                     fun = Fest,
                     nsim = 10)

plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Wells")
pdf("../pictures/100AD/F-function_i_5.pp.pdf")
plot(ffunction, main= "F-function of Wells")
dev.off()
#=====
#K-Function
#=====
#Second approach based on simulations of a theoretical process, i.e. CSR

kfunction <- envelope(i_5.pp,

```

```
        fun = Kest,
        nsim = 10)
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Wells")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/K-function_i_5.pp.pdf")
plot(kfunction, main= "K-function of Wells")
dev.off()
#####
#L-Function
#####
lfunction <- envelope(i_5.pp,
                    fun = Lest,
                    nsim = 10)
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Wells")
pdf("./5pictures/100AD/L-function_i_5.pp.pdf")
plot(lfunction, main= "L-function of Wells")
dev.off()
```

```
#####
##### THE END #####
#####
```